

THE BANGLADESH **ACCOUNTANT**

October - December 2025

QUARTERLY JOURNAL OF THE INSTITUTE OF CHARTERED ACCOUNTANTS OF BANGLADESH

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CONTACT US

CA Bhaban

100 Kazi Nazrul Islam Avenue
Dhaka 1215, Bangladesh

+88 09609612100
+88-02-9115340, 9117521

880 2 9125266

ceo@icab.org.bd

facebook.com/ca.bangladesh

icab.org.bd

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In the quarterly journal, articles of ICAB Members, Members from other Accountancy bodies, Academics and Business Leaders from home and abroad are published.

In half yearly journal, articles focus on macro-economy of the country are published.

The monthly news bulletin publishes different ICAB events of the month. This bulletin acts as an information hub for the Members to keep up-to-date about ICAB and its activities in addition to these publications, ICAB also publishes books, monographs, booklets and Students' Study Manuals regularly.

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“At present, 62 banks are operating in the country, many of which face challenges stemming from inefficiency, weak governance, or chronic loan defaults. International experience shows that numerous countries have resorted to bank mergers as a means of rehabilitating distressed institutions and safeguarding financial stability.”

The October–December issue of The Bangladesh Accountant brings together a broad spectrum of timely and thought-provoking discussions. We have made a sincere effort to present the perspectives and insights of distinguished thinkers on prevailing economic challenges, development prospects, and other pressing national issues.

This issue is published at a critical juncture, as the nation looks forward with anticipation to meaningful reforms across all branches of government. Such expectations have reignited a renewed sense of patriotism and strengthened our collective self-confidence.

In recent times, Bangladesh has continued to grapple with numerous challenges, including declining foreign direct investment, inadequate infrastructure, corruption, overpopulation, slow implementation of economic reforms, high inflation, and persistent budget deficits. Overcoming these obstacles requires unity, commitment, and collaborative efforts that rise above political affiliations and social divisions.

Among the many headwinds facing the economy, the failure of several financial institutions has posed a significant setback to national progress. The Government and Bangladesh Bank maintain that the consolidation of weaker banks will enhance the overall stability of the financial system. However, a critical

question remains: will these mergers genuinely strengthen the banking sector, or might they introduce new risks? With these considerations in mind, and in an effort to provide deeper insight to our readers, ICAB has dedicated this issue to a focused discussion on mergers within Bangladesh’s banking sector.

At present, 62 banks are operating in the country, many of which face challenges stemming from inefficiency, weak governance, or chronic loan defaults. International experience shows that numerous countries have resorted to bank mergers as a means of rehabilitating distressed institutions and safeguarding financial stability. Merging weaker banks with stronger counterparts can help reduce operational costs, enhance efficiency, and reinforce risk-management frameworks. From an economic

standpoint, the principle of economies of scale suggests that larger institutions can operate more efficiently by optimizing resources, technology, and human capital. Moreover, mergers often help restore depositor confidence, as customers feel more secure when a weaker bank becomes part of a stronger and more stable entity, notwithstanding the inherent challenges involved.

Dear readers, as always, we endeavor to enrich you with insightful analyses and scholarly reflections on

contemporary economic issues facing the country. This journal also serves as an important platform for nurturing the writing skills of our members and aspiring contributors.

We firmly believe that improvement is a continuous process. Therefore, we warmly welcome your valuable suggestions to further enhance The Bangladesh Accountant, both at home and abroad. Through our collective efforts and shared commitment, success is well within our reach.

Ala Uddin FCA
Chairman - Editorial Board and
Council Member - ICAB

President's Desk

“Over the past quarter, ICAB has intensified its focus on sustainability frameworks, capacity building, and stakeholder engagement to equip our members with the tools necessary to respond to these evolving demands. We are working collaboratively with regulators, policymakers, and corporate leaders to promote transparency, accountability, and long-term value creation”

Dear Esteemed Members and Professional Colleagues,

As we approach the final quarter of 2025, I extend my warm greetings to all members of The Institute of Chartered Accountants of Bangladesh. This period invites reflection, renewed commitment, and forward-looking resolution as we continue strengthening our profession and contributing meaningfully to the nation's financial landscape and economic development.

The accounting profession stands at a transformative juncture. Rapid advancements in digital technologies, data analytics, artificial intelligence, and sustainability reporting are reshaping the global fiscal panorama. For chartered accountants, these changes are not challenges to fear but opportunities to lead. An optimist always finds opportunities in difficult situations.

ICAB remains steadfast in upgrading professional standards, enhancing quality of Continuing Professional Development (CPD) programs, and ensuring alignment with international best practices. Our commitment to maintaining the highest ethical standards and technical competence continues to define our credibility and public trust.

Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) considerations are no longer peripheral—they are central to responsible business practice. Accountants now play a pivotal role in sustainability

disclosures, integrated reporting, and climate-related financial transparency.

Over the past quarter, ICAB has intensified its focus on sustainability frameworks, capacity building, and stakeholder engagement to equip our members with the tools necessary to respond to these evolving demands. We are working collaboratively with regulators, policymakers, and corporate leaders to promote transparency, accountability, and long-term value creation.

Digital transformation is redefining how assurance, taxation, and advisory services are delivered. From automation in audit procedures to advanced financial analytics, our profession must remain agile.

ICAB continues to encourage innovation within firms of all sizes, supporting technology adoption and knowledge sharing. We recognize that future-ready accountants must

combine technical proficiency with digital fluency and strategic insight.

Our future depends on the next generation of professionals. The Institute is strengthening mentorship initiatives, student engagement programs, and leadership development pathways to nurture young talent. We are equally committed to fostering diversity and inclusiveness within our profession, ensuring equal opportunities for all.

As we conclude 2025, I urge all members to reflect on our collective responsibility. Our profession is not merely about compliance—it is about stewardship. It is about safeguarding public interest, supporting economic resilience, and upholding integrity in every engagement.

Let us continue to elevate the standards of our profession and reinforce the reputation of

Bangladeshi chartered accountants both nationally and internationally.

I extend my sincere appreciation to our Council Members, Editorial Board, and the Secretariat for their dedication and tireless service. Together, we will continue to move forward with confidence and purpose.

Wishing you continued success and professional fulfillment.

With warm regards,

N K A Mobin FCA
President - ICAB

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Impact of Merger of Banks on Economic Stability and Growth

Review and Analysis

M Jalal Hussain FCA

The Author is a
Fellow Member, ICAB

The article was reviewed by
A F Nessaruddin FCA

Introduction

Merger of banks in banking sector is not a new concept. In many accusations, the banks are consolidating around the globe. Mergers and acquisitions (M&A) among banks may be part of the solution to problems of financial distress in Asia and elsewhere. Moreover, we may be on the edge of a new wave of M&A between large banking organizations and other types of financial service providers worldwide.

The U.S. banking industry has undergone dramatic consolidation over the past twenty-five years. After years of virtual calm, Europe's banking sector is ingratiating a new wave of consolidation as well.

Consolidation through M&A has been considered important vehicle for the banking sector specially to protect the interests of deposit holders. Consolidation allows banks to exploit economies of scale and scope, cut costs through operational efficacies and spread the fixed costs entailed by technological change and regulation across a larger expense base, while improving diversification through better geographic reach.

In Bangladesh, central bank of Bangladesh has decided to merge 5 weak, dilapidated and crumbling banks out of more than a dozen banks apart from another dozen of NBFIs to

salvage from this distressed situation. It is expected that the merger of 5 weak and vulnerable banks will improve the banking sector and stabilize the economy to a great extent.

Rationale Behind Bank Consolidation

The rationale behind bank consolidation in the present world is largely influenced by paresthesia over financial agony, insolvency, and the inability of many banks to meet depositors' obligations. These issues contributed to frequent bank letdowns, a loss of public confidence, and an overall inefficiency in financial intermediation. Consequently, the reform sought to create stronger and more resilient banks capable of competing internationally, enhancing public trust, and supporting economic growth through improved credit allocation. Bank consolidation is expected to improve service delivery due to stronger capital bases and better risk management frameworks. Furthermore, it is anticipated that larger, well-capitalized banks would be in a better position to finance large-scale projects, support small and medium enterprises (SMEs), and contribute to macroeconomic solidity.

What are the encounters with the Consolidation?

Stakeholders

Stakeholders of the consolidated banks will be the

Impact of Merger of Banks on Economic Stability and Growth Review and Analysis

great losers. Stakeholders may lose money in a bank consolidation mainly through share dilution, a diminution in stock value, or even the complete erosion of their investment if the banks being consolidated are financially distraught.

Management

With the consolidation, the management will bear perilous challenges with respect to staff integration, rationalization of branches, harmonizing accounting system, cultural compatibility, policies for recognition of non-performing loans, bad loans etc.

Employees

The whole process face resistance from employee unions, who are horrendous of losing their jobs. Their promotion prospects may be affected due to a reduction of

seniority in the merged entity. Further, the rationalization of branches will force to their relocation.

Pecuniary Effects of Consolidation of Banks

Analysis on bank consolidation and economic shocks demonstrates that consolidation can improve bank stability by boosting capital adequacy, though this may come at the cost of efficiency, especially in advanced economies. Consolidation impacts market value, competition, and risk, with its success depending on factors like macroeconomic stability and effective post-merger integration strategies. The effects can vary significantly by country, with consolidation having a more significant impact on efficiency in advanced economies and more pronounced stability gains in emerging economies. Bank

consolidation may cause job redundancy, unemployment and heavy loss for stakeholders in developed and developing countries.

The Favorable and Adverse Economic Effects of Bank consolidation are summarized below:

Favorable Effects

Rationalized Operations and Downsized Overhead Costs

Streamlined operations and reduced overhead costs are a significant advantage of banking consolidation. By amalgamation of multiple institutions, redundant processes and systems can be eliminated, leading to increased efficiency. This allows banks to centralize functions such as back-office operations, technology infrastructure, and administrative tasks. As a result, they can achieve cost savings through economies of scale.

Entree to Advanced Technology and Financial Services

Entree to advanced technology and financial services is one of the key benefits of banking consolidation. Consolidated banks can leverage their resources to invest in cutting-edge systems and set-up monitoring, enabling them to offer customers a wide range of innovative products and services. This includes advanced online banking

platforms, mobile apps with enhanced features, and personalized financial planning tools. Consolidated banks can provide access to specialized services such as wealth management, investment advisory, and international banking solutions.

Greater Financial Equanimity

One of the best advantages of banking consolidation is the potential for improved financial equanimity. By combining resources and diversifying risks across a larger organization, consolidated banks can withstand economic downturns and financial shocks more efficiently and effectively. Economic stability is achieved through a larger capital base, a stronger balance sheet, and the

ability to mitigate risks through diversified operations. This will improve peoples' confidence on banks and increase investment in banks.

Bigger Capital Base and Sturdier Balance Sheet

Larger capital base and a stronger balance sheet are significant advantages of banking consolidation. This increased financial strength provides stability and reassurance to customers, as it reduces the likelihood of bank failures or the need for government bailouts. A stronger balance sheet allows banks to offer a more extensive range of products and services, including loans and investments, benefiting customers who may have more diverse financial

needs. This will improve investment scenario of banking sector.

Divergence and Risk Mitigation

Diversification and risk mitigation are imperative benefits of banking consolidation. When banks merge or acquire each other, they expand their portfolios and reduce reliance on a single sector or market. This diversification helps to spread risk and minimize the impact of economic downturns or sector-specific challenges. For investors, this means their deposits and investments are less defenseless to the performance of a single institution or industry.

Capability to Serve a Broader Range of Clienteles

Banking consolidation can enable financial institutions to serve a broader customer base by leveraging their expanded resources and capabilities. With a larger scope, banks can offer a wider range of products and services tailored to different customer needs. They can provide specialized financial solutions for both personal and commercial clients, catering to various industries and segments. Consolidation can lead to increased geographical reach, allowing banks to better serve customers in different regions.

Impact of Merger of Banks on Economic Stability and Growth Review and Analysis

The Adverse Economic Effects of Banking Consolidation

Job Losses and Employee Quandary

Consolidation of banks often centralize to duplicate jobs being eliminated, causing layoffs and creating uncertainty for remaining employees regarding their future roles and company culture. Bank consolidation leads to significant job losses due to the elimination of redundant roles and the closure of overlapping branches. This is a prime concern for bank employees, who may experience heightened job insecurity, stress, and resistance to change during the consolidation process as it's difficult to get a new job now a days.

Customer Disorientation and Dread

Clients may become jumbled or be frightened about the status of their accounts, deposits, loans and the future quality of service, leading to a loss of trust. Big customer may divert their investments in government savings instruments. Approximately 30 million people in Bangladesh are unbanked, meaning they don't have an account with a financial institution or mobile financial service. This represents about 45% of the adult population, according to the World Bank. Consolidation of banks may

increase the unbanked number of people.

Fiasco to Address Root Causes

Consolidating weak banks does not guarantee success if the underlying problems like high default loans and NFLs are not properly managed after the merger, as seen with the BDBL merger in Bangladesh.

Corrosion of faith

Banking is built on trust, and if mergers are poorly managed or result in public sector failures, it can corrode public confidence in the entire banking sector.

Stakeholders at Risk

The merger process may also have negative consequences for shareholders, depositors, and employees of weak banks. Shareholders may see their ownership stake diluted, depositors may face delays in accessing their funds or even experience losses, and employees may lose their jobs due to branch closures. And such a damp mood is evident in the market, as the investors are looking at the merger of weak banks with strong banks negatively. In Bangladesh, after the merger of Padma Bank with Exim Bank, the latter's shares slipped 3% below their face value. The very day Exim Bank signed the MoU, its shares dropped to Tk9.70 at the Dhaka Stock Exchange (DSE) from a face value of Tk10.

Possible Decline in Competition

Banking consolidation can lead to a diminution in competition within the finance industry. When large banks merge or acquire smaller ones, it reduces the number of players in the market. With fewer competitors, customers may have limited choices and face the possibility of higher prices for banking services. Moreover, decreased competition can also hinder innovation and limit the diversity of products and services available to customers. This consolidation trend raises concerns about monopolistic tendencies and the overall health of the banking sector, as excessive concentration of economic power can potentially result in market manipulation and reduced consumer safety.

Limited Choices and Higher Prices for Clienteles

When banks consolidate, customers may face limited choices and higher prices. With fewer banks operating in the market, customers have fewer options for their banking needs. This reduction in competition can lead to increased prices for services such as loans, credit cards, and account fees. For example, in a consolidated banking market, customers may find it harder to negotiate favorable terms or lower interest rates due to the lack of alternative options.

Consequently, customers may need to carefully evaluate the potential cost implications before committing to banking services provided by consolidated institutions.

Increased Systemic Risk

Increased systemic risk is a concern associated with banking consolidation. When multiple banks merge or acquire smaller institutions, the resulting entity becomes larger and interconnected, potentially leading to a concentration of economic power. If this consolidated bank faces financial challenges or fails, it can have widespread repercussions on the entire financial system. Additionally, the concentration of economic power within a few dominant players can also increase the risk of market manipulation. It's crucial for regulators to closely monitor these risks to maintain

a stable and resilient financial system.

Too Big to Fail

One probable drawback of banking consolidation is the risk of institutions becoming "too big to fail," meaning their letdown could have spartan implications for the entire economy. This could lead to government bailouts to prevent a collapse and mitigate the systemic risk. Historically, this has happened during financial crises, such as the 2008 global financial crisis. The fear of potential bailouts may create a moral hazard, as it allows consolidated banks to take on more risks with the assumption that they will be rescued by the government if anything goes wrong. This can destabilize market discipline and create an bumpy playing field for smaller, non-consolidated institutions.

Consolidation of Banks Perspective to Bangladesh

In the initial phase, six banks—First Security Islami Bank, Global Islami Bank, Union Bank, Exim Bank, Social Islami Bank, and ICB Islami Bank—were assessed by global audit firms Ernst & Young and KPMG. Their AQR results show significant underperformance, highlighting issues such as capital shortfalls, high levels of classified loans, large provision gaps, and liquidity shortages. As a result, these banks have failed to pay their depositors and return funds to their lenders, which has gravely shaken public confidence in the banking sector. This presents a serious threat to the stability of the country's financial system.

The interim government's advisory council has approved a proposal to merge five troubled

BB dissolves boards of five troubled Islamic banks, appoints administrators

BANKS SET FOR MERGER

- ▶ Social Islami Bank
- ▶ Union Bank
- ▶ First Security Islami Bank
- ▶ Global Islami Bank
- ▶ Exim Bank

MERGER OF 5 ISLAMIC BANKS BEGINS

FATE OF DEPOSITORS, SHAREHOLDERS

- ▶ Full repayment of small depositors (≤ Tk2 lakh) to start in a month
- ▶ Larger depositors to get phased withdrawals
- ▶ Publicly listed, but bank shareholders to receive nothing

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Impact of Merger of Banks on Economic Stability and Growth Review and Analysis

private banks. The banks—First Security Islami Bank, Global Islami Bank, Union Bank, EXIM Bank, and Social Islami Bank—will be combined to form a new Shariah-based bank. Two names have been proposed for the new bank: “United Islamic Bank” and “Combined Islamic Bank.” The bank will be operated on a commercial and professional basis. The government will provide Tk 200 billion in capital, with Tk 150 billion coming from institutional deposits converted to capital via a “bail-in” process. The merger is intended to address the severe financial distress, high non-performing loan (NPL) ratios, and lack of public confidence in the affected banks.

About the fate of sponsor directors and ordinary shareholders in the merged banks, the governor said, “We are following international practice under the Bank Resolution Ordinance, where decisions are based on the actual value of shareholders’ holdings. Bangladesh Bank Governor said that sponsors and ordinary shareholders’ shares values are now zero”.

Investors are on the verge of losing shares of five banks. Bangladesh Bank has dissolved the boards of directors of five

private banks listed on the capital market, which are plagued by irregularities and corruption, and appointed administrators. The Governor assured the protection of the interests of the depositors of these banks. At a recent press conference, Governor of Central Bank said that the equity value of the shareholders of the merged banks is now appears negative. Therefore, the value of the shares will be considered zero. No compensation will be paid to anyone. The day after such an announcement, on Thursday, the share trading of the five Islamic banks that are in the process of merging was suspended indefinitely. Investors are on the verge of losing their investment of these banks. Unless small investors of the said five banks are compensated by GOB, the dying stock market of Bangladesh will completely collapse.

Conclusion

Bangladesh has 62 scheduled banks and 35 non-bank-financial institutes (NBFI), which is considered over-numbered for its economy size. What the country needs are fewer, stronger, better-run and corruption-free institutions. The banks consolidation of the government presents an

opportunity to create a precedent for that evolution. The banking services are not equally provided to all customers either. While large businesses could avail high volumes of loans and become willful defaulters, small and medium-sized businesses, without obvious political connections, could not access funds. Therefore, the issue of accountability is very important for the banking sector. Until those who mismanaged or looted these banks are punished, public trust will remain low. The country can’t afford returning to the past banking culture that pleased the marauders and penalized authentic savers. The laws relating to financial institutions are required to be reframed and reorganized to punish the looters and save the savers.

The reform in the banking sector can’t succeed without broader governance restructuring. Scrawny rule of law, political influence over the regulators, and engrained patronage networks have long destabilized and destroyed viability of few banks in Bangladesh’s financial sector. Unless these systemic issues are addressed, no merger, will bring about lasting changes and fruitful results in banking sector.

Enhancing Audit Effectiveness A Strategic Review of Technical Issues in Modern Audit Planning

Muhammed Omar Faruk Ripon FCA

The Author is a Fellow Member, ICAB

Abstract

This article critically examines fifteen (15) technical components that drive risk-based audit planning, supporting internal auditors to align with global best practices. From frameworks like COSO and IIA's Three Lines Model to data analytics and KPI-based prioritization, this review builds a roadmap for forward-thinking audit functions.

Recommendations, insights, and future directions are proposed to ensure adaptability in an evolving corporate governance environment.

Preamble

Internal auditing has transitioned from compliance monitoring to a strategic advisory role. As businesses face complex risk landscapes, audit planning must integrate

Integrated Audit Framework

The article was reviewed by
Mohammad Zahid Hossain FCA

Enhancing Audit Effectiveness

A Strategic Review of Technical Issues in Modern Audit Planning

<p>structured, data-driven, and framework-aligned methods to ensure efficiency, value creation, and stakeholder trust. Audit planning is not merely about scheduling engagements; it is about choosing the right battles to fight. Ineffective planning can waste resources and overlook critical risks. The Institute of Internal Auditors (IIA) and Committee of Sponsoring Organizations (COSO) have provided guiding frameworks,</p>	<p>yet execution depends on integrating technical tools like risk matrices, analytics, and process-level registers.</p> <p>Advanced Audit Planning Frameworks & Technical Issues</p> <p>Modern audit planning goes beyond checklists and schedules; it requires structured frameworks and specialized technical tools. By combining</p>	<p>models like COSO, IIA's Three Lines, and RCM with analytics-driven methods such as CAATs and KPI analysis, auditors can design plans that are both risk-focused and strategically aligned. These frameworks ensure that audits not only address compliance but also add measurable value to governance, risk management, and performance improvement.</p>
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No.	Technical Element	Use in Audit Planning
1	7Rs of Audit	Ensures the audit is Relevant, Timed, Scoped, and Reported properly.
2	5Cs of Audit Observation	Criteria, Condition, Cause, Consequence, and Corrective Action—used for framing findings.
3	Audit Universe	A comprehensive listing of all auditable entities/processes in an organization, used for risk-based planning.
4	Risk Control Matrix (RCM)	Tool for mapping processes to risks and controls, identifying control gaps.
5	COSO Framework Integration	Mapping audit focus areas to COSO's five components: Control Environment, Risk Assessment, Control Activities, Info & Communication, Monitoring.
6	IIA's Three Lines Model	Clarifies roles of management (1st line), risk/compliance (2nd), and internal audit (3rd).
7	Audit Risk Assessment Matrix	Categorizes risk likelihood vs. impact to prioritize audit areas.
8	Internal Control Questionnaire (ICQ)	Standardized questions used during planning to assess the design of internal controls.
9	Audit Planning Memorandum (APM)	Document summarizing scope, objectives, risks, resources, timeline, and methodology for each audit.
10	SWOT Analysis of Audit Function	Used internally to assess audit team's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats.
11	Root Cause Analysis (RCA)	Used post-audit to analyze repeated control failures or systemic issues.
12	Annual Audit Plan Calendar	Month-wise schedule of audit engagements based on resource availability and risk prioritization.
13	Engagement-Level Risk Register	Customized register per audit, listing identified risks, controls, and their treatment.
14	Data Analytics (CAATs)	Use of Excel, IDEA, ACL, or Power BI to analyze large data sets in planning and fieldwork.
15	KPI and KRI Analysis	Helps in selecting audit areas by evaluating key performance and risk indicators.

The 7Rs of Audit and Supporting Tools: Strengthening Assurance and Governance

The 7Rs of Audit represent seven guiding principles that internal auditors can apply to ensure audits are effective, risk-based, and aligned with governance priorities. They help auditors ask the “right” questions at every stage of the engagement.

R	Full Term	Focus of Audit	Example
1	Right Process	Audit the correct area or function	Reviewing Procurement, not unrelated HR
2	Right Time	Conduct audit when risk is highest	Inventory audit before year-end
3	Right Scope	Define balanced, risk-based coverage	Vendor selection only, not entire procurement
4	Right Resources	Assign qualified auditors/tools	CIA + data analytics for IT audit
5	Right Objectives	Align objectives with risk/stakeholder needs	Check compliance in credit approval
6	Right Methodology	Apply recognized methods/frameworks	Sampling, analytics, ISO/IIA standards
7	Right Reporting	Deliver clear, timely, risk-ranked findings	Concise report to management/board

The 7Rs of Audit Framework

The 5Cs of Audit Observation

A structured way to present audit findings:

- Criteria - What should happen (policy/standard).
- Condition - What is actually happening.
- Cause - Why the above gap exists.
- Consequence - Impact of the issue.
- Corrective Action - Recommendation to resolve.

This sequence ensures observations are logical, actionable, and transparent.

Audit Universe

The Audit Universe is a comprehensive inventory of all auditable entities (business units, subsidiaries, processes, compliance areas, IT systems). It supports:

Enhancing Audit Effectiveness

A Strategic Review of Technical Issues in Modern Audit Planning

- Risk prioritization (high-risk areas first),
- Efficient resource allocation,
- Annual & long-term planning,
- Coverage monitoring, and
- Regulatory compliance assurance.

Risk Control Matrix (RCM)

The RCM links risks with their mitigating controls. It documents process risks, control objectives, control owners, and effectiveness. Benefits include:

- Enabling risk-based audits,
- Supporting SOX/IFC compliance,
- Providing management assurance, and
- Facilitating continuous monitoring.

COSO Framework Integration

The COSO model (Control Environment, Risk Assessment, Control Activities, Information & Communication, Monitoring) provides an internationally recognized standard for internal control. It ensures compliance, holistic assurance, and alignment with IIA standards while strengthening board confidence.

IIA's Three Lines Model

This model clarifies accountability for risk:

- First Line - Management owns risks.
- Second Line - Risk & compliance oversee controls.
- Third Line - Internal audit provides independent assurance.

Its emphasis on governance and collaboration enhances risk management effectiveness.

Risk Assessment Matrix

A likelihood-impact matrix prioritizes audit areas by scoring risks (e.g., 5x5 grid). It helps auditors decide what to audit, how often, and with what depth, ensuring alignment with Enterprise Risk Management (ERM).

Internal Control Questionnaire (ICQ)

An ICQ helps auditors test whether controls exist and operate effectively. Tailored questionnaires (e.g., procurement, payroll, IT) highlight control gaps early and support audit planning.

Audit Planning Memorandum (APM)

The APM is the blueprint for each audit—defining scope, objectives, risks, resources, and timelines. It ensures alignment, team coordination, and proper documentation of audit intent.

SWOT Analysis for Internal Audit

A SWOT assessment (Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, Threats) supports audit strategy, resource planning, and communication with boards. It helps position internal audit as a proactive governance partner.

Root Cause Analysis (RCA)

RCA tools (5 Whys, Fishbone, Pareto) ensure findings address underlying causes, not symptoms. This reduces repeat findings and promotes sustainable improvements.

Annual Audit Plan Calendar

A structured calendar (fixed or rolling) maps audit engagements across the year, aligning them with risk cycles and ensuring resource optimization.

Engagement-Level Risk Register

Developed during planning, this register records inherent risks, controls, residual risks, and planned tests for a specific

audit. It improves scope clarity and documentation.

Data Analytics (Computer Assisted Audit Techniques or CAATs)

CAATs enhance audit by testing 100% of data, detecting anomalies, and enabling continuous monitoring. Tools include Excel, Power BI, ACL, IDEA, SQL, and Python.

KPI and KRI Analysis

KPIs measure performance; KRIs signal risk exposure. By analyzing both, auditors prioritize high-risk processes, explain findings, and support continuous monitoring.

Importance of These Issues

In today's complex regulatory and business environment, the

role of technical tools in audit planning and execution has become increasingly vital. These tools not only enhance efficiency and accuracy but also ensure that audits remain strategically aligned with organizational objectives, risks, and compliance requirements. Their contribution spans across risk responsiveness, governance, resource optimization, stakeholder confidence, and regulatory compliance.

▪ Risk Responsiveness:

Technical tools strengthen an auditor's ability to prioritize high-impact risks. By using data analytics, continuous monitoring dashboards, and AI-based anomaly detection, audit teams can identify where potential losses, fraud, or compliance failures are most likely to occur. This responsiveness ensures that audit resources are directed at areas with the greatest potential impact, making the process more preventive than reactive.

▪ Governance Support:

Well-structured technical tools enhance board-level governance by linking audit insights directly to strategic concerns such as compliance, performance efficiency, and enterprise risk. Tools like risk registers, GRC (Governance, Risk, and Compliance) software, and real-time reporting platforms

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give the board and audit committees a clear line of sight into organizational vulnerabilities and performance gaps. This strengthens accountability and decision-making at the highest level.

- **Resource Optimization:** By leveraging scheduling software, audit management systems, and automated working paper solutions, organizations ensure that

audit manpower and hours are used in the most efficient way. Resource optimization reduces duplication of effort, improves coverage of key processes, and allows for the timely completion of audits. This efficiency leads to cost savings and makes audit teams more agile in addressing emerging priorities.

- **Stakeholder Confidence:** Structured, evidence-based

planning supported by technical tools increases stakeholder trust. When audit findings are backed by data analytics, visual dashboards, and digital audit trails, management, regulators, and investors view the process as credible and transparent. This not only builds confidence in the audit function but also strengthens the organization's overall reputation for integrity and accountability.

▪ **Regulatory Compliance:** Regulations such as SOX, ISO 31000, BSEC guidelines, and other international frameworks require organizations to maintain robust internal controls, risk assessments, and compliance documentation. Technical tools enable seamless tracking of compliance requirements, automate reporting, and reduce the risk of non-compliance penalties. By aligning internal audit practices with global standards, organizations stay ahead of regulatory demands and demonstrate a culture of compliance.

Strategic Recommendations

To maximize audit effectiveness, strategic recommendations must bridge policy, planning, people, and technology. By aligning standards with organizational objectives and embedding risk-based tools, audits become both proactive

and value-driven. These initiatives ensure that audit functions not only safeguard compliance but also support long-term business resilience and stakeholder trust.

Practical Tips

Effective audit planning is not just about frameworks and tools but also about applying practical techniques that enhance precision and adaptability. Simple measures—like maintaining rolling calendars, linking findings to root causes, and reassessing risks mid-engagement—help ensure audits remain relevant, sustainable, and value-adding. These tips strengthen both the efficiency and credibility of the overall audit process.

- Use a rolling calendar to adapt to changing risk landscape

- Conduct an ICQ before each engagement to refine scope
- Link each audit finding to a root cause for sustainability
- Keep an audit trail of APMs, Risk Registers, and Matrix versions
- Re-assess engagement-level risks midway if process changes occur

What's Next in Audit Planning

As business environments evolve, audit planning must adapt to address emerging risks and opportunities. New areas such as ESG, AI-driven insights, and cybersecurity demand expanded frameworks, specialized skills, and smarter use of technology. These trends push audit functions toward continuous monitoring and real-time assurance, ensuring relevance and resilience in a rapidly changing landscape.

Area	Actionable Recommendation
Policy Alignment	Integrate COSO, IIA standards, and ERM into audit charters
Annual Planning	Use Audit Universe + Risk Matrix + Calendar for proactive planning
Team Capability	Train auditors on CAATs, analytics, and control frameworks
Automation	Use Power BI, ACL, or Audit Management Systems for dashboards
KPI-Driven Focus	Tie audit focus to strategic metrics and thresholds
Stakeholder Dialogue	Conduct annual risk workshops and feedback loops

Emerging Trend	Implication for Planning
ESG & Sustainability Audits	Need for new KPIs, compliance registers, and skillsets
AI in Auditing	Use of predictive analytics and anomaly detection
Cybersecurity & Digital Risks	Engagement registers to expand to digital assets
Continuous Auditing	More real-time dashboards and data feeds required

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Conclusion

Technical audit planning is no longer optional—it's essential. By integrating structured models (COSO, 3 Lines), tools (CAATs, KPIs), and control mapping (RCM, ICQ), internal audit functions can deliver strategic insight, prevent surprises, and enhance governance. Together, the 7Rs of Audit, 5Cs of Observation, Audit Universe, RCM, COSO Framework, and related tools create a structured, risk-based, and value-adding audit approach. Their application strengthens governance, enhances accountability, and ensures audits remain relevant in an evolving regulatory and business landscape.

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From Evidence to Algorithms The Forensic Turn in Internal Audit

S M Ashfaqur Rahman FCA

The Author is a
Fellow Member, ICAB

Introduction

The dynamic business environment of today, especially in Bangladesh, calls for a forensic mindset in addition to the traditional auditing focus on rule compliance and numerical checks. It is difficult to discern between inadvertent mistakes and deliberate fraud due to rapid corporate expansion, complex ownership structures, and usually insufficient controls. Because they depend on sampling and accuracy checks, standard audits frequently miss early warning signs of illegal activity. In fact, according to Mvunabandi and Nomlala (2022), "financial statement fraud and traditional audit failures to detect fraud in entities have increased." A growing field as a result of more financial and professional

infractions is forensic accounting (Jain & Lamba, 2020). By asking questions about the "why" rather than just the "what," a forensic approach pushes auditors to look beyond documentation. To find underlying truths, this approach blends scepticism, analytical rigour, and curiosity. Adopting this viewpoint is now essential for maintaining trust, encouraging moral behaviour, and guaranteeing sustainable growth in Bangladesh; it is no longer optional.

Distinguishing a Financial Statement Audit from a Forensic Investigation

Before discussing the value of forensic thinking in auditing, it is important to clearly explain the difference between a financial

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Muallem Ahmed Choudhury FCA

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statement audit and a forensic accounting investigation, as they serve very different purposes. A financial statement audit is carried out to provide reasonable assurance that a company's financial statements are fairly presented and free from major errors or misstatements, whether caused by mistake or intentional misrepresentation. Audits are planned using materiality limits, sample testing, and compliance checks, and their main objective is to enhance confidence in financial reporting—not to conduct an investigation.

A forensic accounting investigation, in contrast, is a targeted and purpose-driven exercise that begins only when there are clear warning signs or specific concerns. These may include whistleblower complaints, regulatory scrutiny, unexplained financial losses, unusual transaction patterns, signs of management override, cyber incidents, or suspected

misuse of assets. Unlike financial statement audits, forensic investigations are not restricted by materiality thresholds or sampling techniques. Their purpose is to determine whether wrongdoing has occurred, how it was carried out, who was involved, and what financial impact resulted, often for legal, regulatory, or disciplinary action.

It is therefore important to understand that a financial statement audit is not a forensic accounting investigation. Auditors are not expected to review every transaction or uncover all wrongdoing. While auditors are required to remain professionally sceptical and alert to risk indicators, detailed investigative procedures are applied only when a separate forensic accounting engagement is initiated. A forensic mindset in auditing simply means recognizing warning signs early and responding appropriately—not

converting routine audits into investigations.

The Need for a Forensic Mindset in Auditing

The business world of today is much more complicated than it was in the past. Errors are no longer limited to missing documents or incorrect numbers; many are now planned, concealed, and bolstered by cunning strategies. The traditional auditing method, which merely verifies accuracy and compliance, is insufficient in such a setting (Ergin, 2019; Kassem & Omoteso, 2023). Nowadays, auditors must have a forensic mindset, which combines inquiry, healthy scepticism, and curiosity (Alkhalaileh et al., 2024). Asking more in-depth questions is part of this strategy: Why was this deal made? In reality, who gains? What could be concealed in records that appear to be clean? A forensic auditor makes connections, examines behaviour, and identifies odd trends in information or discrepancies in people's accounts (Imoniana & Silva, 2013; Ozili, 2015).

The evidence makes it abundantly evident how urgent this change is. According to Bangladesh Bank, the country's banking industry lost roughly US\$17 billion due to dubious lending practices and insider deals. As a result, the central bank hired significant international audit firms to track

down the money (Reuters, 2025). A Bangladesh Bank investigation into the digital finance industry found that Tk 645 crore in illegal e-money issuance and Tk 1,711 crore in government social safety net payments disappeared via the Nagad mobile financial service platform (Bangladesh Bank, 2024). In a previous cyber-heist against Bangladesh Bank in 2016, fraudulent SWIFT messages attempted to transfer almost US\$1 billion; while the majority were blocked, US\$81 million was successfully taken and subsequently linked to the Philippines (Reuters, 2016). Investigators claim that former banker Prashanta Kumar Halder embezzled more than Tk 102 billion from several financial institutions in domestic corporate scandals (The Daily Star, 2022).

Cases like these highlight the importance of forensic thinking in Bangladesh's audit environment, where a large number of businesses are still family-owned and unofficial, and lax internal controls make it difficult to distinguish between personal and business finances. This environment frequently results in inflated costs, fake sales reports, and fake invoices. Therefore, in order to identify deception early on, a forensic auditor looks beyond the numbers and considers motives, patterns, and anomalies (Eghe-Ikharhe et al., 2024). According to Odeyemi et al. (2024), being forensic does not

entail treating every audit as a crime scene; rather, it incorporates standard audit procedures with data analytics, investigative interviewing, and behavioural insight. This way of thinking improves governance, restores public confidence, and shields investors from enormous financial losses.

Fraud prevention cannot rest on auditors alone. Large financial irregularities—especially trade-based money laundering through under- and over-invoicing—usually occur within complex systems involving many institutions and processes. Such practices often take advantage of weaknesses across the broader financial and regulatory environment, including banking operations, customs procedures, trade documentation, and tax administration. In Bangladesh, limitations in customs valuation, incomplete checking of export-import records, and coordination gaps among the National Board of Revenue (NBR), banks, and regulators have created vulnerabilities that go beyond what audits can realistically address. Even when auditors apply strong professional scepticism, identifying irregularities becomes difficult if the underlying data is fragmented or unreliable. Without greater automation, better data sharing, and clearly defined accountability, these risks are likely to continue. Forensic thinking in auditing is therefore

most effective when it operates alongside stronger institutional controls and regulatory cooperation, rather than in isolation.

Common Fraud Schemes

The motivations behind corporate fraud are always the same: opportunity, pressure, and greed. These frauds manifest through asset theft, financial manipulation, and corruption in Bangladesh's business environment, where informal practices frequently coexist with lax controls (Imoniana & Silva, 2013). Acknowledging these schemes enables auditors to protect organizational credibility and identify risks early.

Statement of Financial Position
The real performance of an organisation is distorted by fraud. It happens when management falsifies financial statements to satisfy loan requirements or impress investors. Examples include overstating inventory, postponing expense recording, or recognising revenue before delivery. Under year-end pressure to "show profit," such strategies are typical in industries like textiles, ceramics, and construction, frequently supported by a lack of auditor independence (Muttakin et al., 2017).

Although it occurs more frequently, asset misappropriation is less valuable. It includes cash theft,

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unrecorded scrap sales, and fraudulent vendor billing. Some employees take advantage of the lack of independent verification or unexpected audits by fabricating suppliers or inflating prices with colluding vendors.

In opaque processes, procurement fraud flourishes. Where oversight is lacking, kickbacks, phoney tenders, and exaggerated invoices thrive. Under the pretext of "urgent" approvals, construction and logistics companies frequently encounter such problems (Ahmed et al., 2020).

Payroll fraud, which includes phoney overtime, manipulated attendance, and ghost workers, is pervasive in tea estates and factories. Skimming is made simple by cash-based systems, particularly when accounts and HR work together.

Under pressure from business, corruption and bribery continue to be accepted as "speed money" or "commissions" to obtain permits or VAT refunds, normalising unethical behaviour.

Fake invoices, manipulated ERP entries, and diverted online payments are all examples of the new frontier of IT and cyber fraud, which targets businesses with inadequate system controls and access management (Ghosh, 2019).

These schemes all take advantage of covertness and opportunity. In order to identify them, auditors must develop a forensic mentality, which involves challenging patterns, examining anomalies in data, and interpreting behaviour. By doing this, auditing transforms from a box-checking exercise into a truth-seeking discipline, which is crucial for re-establishing confidence in

Bangladesh's expanding corporate sector.

Contributing Factors

Fraud rarely happens by accident; rather, it flourishes in environments with lax ethics, scant oversight, and accountability that yields to expediency. Fraud in Bangladesh's corporate environment is typically opportunistic rather than clever, taking advantage of known flaws in culture and governance. Organisations can develop true resilience instead of reactive compliance by identifying these enablers.

One of the main weaknesses is inadequate internal controls. In many family-run businesses, one or two people hold all the power, approving purchases, authorising payments, and handling account reconciliation. Because they frequently lack automation and independent review, even large conglomerates provide an ideal environment for manipulation. The incidence of financial fraud was found to be significantly inversely correlated with the robustness of internal control systems, particularly oversight and segregation of duties, according to empirical research conducted among 200 SMEs in Bangladesh (Hossain, 2025).

The issue is made worse by inadequate corporate governance. Boards may only exist in name, audit committees hardly ever question

management, and control overrides are often ignored. The "tone at the top" normalises shortcuts and discourages accountability when leaders prioritise numbers over ethics (Rashid, 2022).

Another catalyst is performance pressure. Managers may fabricate inventory, postpone losses, or inflate revenues in order to reach aggressive loan or sales targets. This desperation is eventually justified as survival or loyalty (Lin et al., 2022).

Fraud continues because of poor oversight and audit quality. The independence of many internal audit teams is compromised because they report to management rather than the Board. In order to preserve client relationships, external auditors frequently soften findings by using minimal

checklists rather than forensic analysis. The 2016 Bangladesh Bank cyber heist cost the country's central bank approximately US \$81 million, demonstrating the disastrous consequences of technical and oversight errors (Macknight, 2021; Bangladesh Bank cyber heist report, 2016).

Ethical boundaries are further blurred by cultural tolerance of "speed money" and informal payments, and regulatory enforcement gaps leave punishment unclear. In the meantime, in the digital age, technological flaws like inadequate cybersecurity, lax ERP access control, and a dearth of data analytics open up new fraud opportunities. For instance, a survey of the mobile financial services (MFS) industry in Bangladesh revealed that 17.0% of agents reported fraud incidents, compared to 6.3% of

individual users (The Financial Express, 2024).

In the end, corporate fraud in Bangladesh is a reflection of both cultural permissiveness and structural fragility. More than just control systems are needed for true protection; forensic thinking, transparent governance, empowered auditors, and moral leadership are also necessary. Prevention will eventually surpass detection only when integrity is ingrained rather than enforced.

Integrating Investigative Thinking into Audit Processes

These days, modern auditing requires more than just checking boxes; it calls for investigative reasoning, curiosity, and a degree of scepticism that is "appropriate" (Hurt et al., 2012) for conducting an audit. This encourages auditors to "think more broadly and incorporate information from a variety of sources" (Griffith et al., 2014). In the business world of Bangladesh, where "accounting fraud is a major problem" for listed companies (Uddin et al., 2025) and frequently goes unnoticed due to cultural norms and paperwork, auditors need to think more like detectives than verifiers. Auditors need to "think critically about the evidence" instead of just accepting it, and investigative thinking entails asking questions that go beyond the evidence.

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Auditors should ask whether documents make sense rather than merely verifying their existence, which can be "ineffective in detecting fraud" (Shehata, 2020). Even if an invoice appears correct, it may conceal collusion or exorbitant prices. Auditors can find discrepancies that are not visible to routine reviews by tracking down the people who started, authorised, and profited from a transaction. Research highlights the significance of "exercising the appropriate level of professional scepticism when conducting an audit," stating that "professional scepticism is central to this approach" (Hurt et al., 2012). According to Nickell (2012), the "nature of the auditor-client relationship threatens an auditor's ability to maintain an attitude of professional scepticism" because long-term client relationships frequently lead to an over-reliance on management explanations.

Investigative auditors use techniques like "specific analytical procedures" to counter this by looking for independent evidence, examining data trends, and confirming external confirmations (Kassem & Omoteso, 2023). This mindset is ingrained through interviews, behaviour analysis (realising that "non-financial information is crucial to reduce the fraud risk management" (Shehata, 2020), and "fraud detection automation through data analytics" (Ikhsan et al., 2022). It begins with fraud-risk brainstorming during audit planning.

Quantitative red flags like round-number entries or duplicate vendors are combined with qualitative clues like hesitation or contradiction. Documentation must explain the rationale behind an investigation and the methods used to arrive at conclusions,

not just the outcomes. Since "the manifestation of a sceptical and objective attitude contributes to the exercise of control over the decisions taken and the results obtained," investigative thinking enhances traditional auditing rather than replaces it (Deliu, 2020). This mentality restores independence and transforms auditors into defenders of openness and confidence in Bangladesh, where informal systems and personal influence predominate.

Risk Assessment and Fraud Identification

In order to promote proactive auditing behaviours and an unbiased assessment of the evidence, modern auditing calls for more than just verifying compliance; it also calls for curiosity, scepticism, and investigative reasoning (Peecher et al., 2023). In the business environment of Bangladesh, where accounting fraud is a significant issue and frequently goes undetected by the complexity of systems, appears as ordinary paperwork, or is hidden by intricate schemes, auditors need to take an investigative approach instead of just keeping records (Fadilah et al., 2019). Asking more in-depth questions about the existence of documents as well as their logic, consistency, and authenticity is a sign of investigative thinking.

Even a legitimate invoice can conceal collusion or exaggerated expenses. Auditors can find hidden inconsistencies by tracking down the people who started, authorised, and profited from a transaction across several levels of control. In order to identify financial statement fraud, professional scepticism is crucial (Brazel et al., 2024). Auditors must look for independent evidence from several reliable, independent sources and examine data for odd patterns, duplicate transactions, or outliers rather than depending solely on management justifications (Kassem & Omoteso, 2023). This strategy is supported by methods such as data analytics, behavioural cues (evaluating attitudes and inconsistent responses), and interviews, which improve fraud detection and investigative effectiveness in forensic accounting (Mubarrat, 2025).

Bangladeshi empirical data emphasises how urgent this change is. Improved forensic accounting abilities are statistically significantly linked to higher detection rates of white-collar crimes, according to a 2023 study conducted by the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Bangladesh (ICAB, 2023). According to *Rising Issues of White-Collar Crime in Bangladesh (2025)*, reported financial crimes in industries like banking and corporate firms increased by roughly 45% between 2018 and 2023, with cumulative losses soaring to over Tk 25,000 crore. Only 12–15% of reported cases resulted in convictions, which underscores systemic barriers and the necessity of auditor vigilance (*Rising Issues of White-Collar Crime in Bangladesh, 2025*). Standard auditing is strengthened (not replaced) by investigative thinking. This mentality helps

auditors preserve independence, lessen bias, and safeguard organisations through sincere insight and integrity in Bangladesh, where informal controls, deference, and hierarchy can obfuscate the truth and raise the risk of control overrides.

Technological tools are developing in support of research to supplement these institutional pressures. Today, auditors can identify irregularities in journal entries from several companies without breaching confidentiality thanks to federated learning techniques (Mashiko et al., 2025). In large, unbalanced datasets, deep-boosting decision tree models—which combine neural nets and gradient boosting—are showing promise in identifying infrequent fraudulent transactions (Xu et al., 2023). These tools enhance auditors' ability to identify questionable items for further examination, but they do not take the place of their judgement.

Developing Audit Procedures with a Forensic Lens

Auditing is radically changed from routine compliance checks to a mindset of discovery and critical inquiry when audit procedures are developed using a forensic lens (Imoniana & Silva, 2013). This method is essential for detecting fraud and financial irregularities that conventional compliance audits might

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overlook (Oyedokun, 2015). A forensic perspective is especially important in Bangladesh, where issues like lax corporate regulation, inadequate investor protection, methodological flaws in traditional auditing, and cases of auditors failing to identify profit overstatements exist (Siddiqui & Podder, 2002). This situation, which is frequently impacted by regional sociopolitical institutions and is marked by pervasive corruption and a lack of accountability, emphasises how poorly conventional auditing techniques can identify intricate fraud schemes (Debnath et al., 2019).

Every step of a forensic approach requires strategic scepticism, raising doubts about the authenticity and underlying intent of the data in addition to its accuracy. Because they actively seek out new information and evaluate the evidence objectively, auditors with higher levels of scepticism are better at spotting fraud (Brewster et al., 2021). This entails actively seeking independent verification using techniques like positive confirmation, reviewing supporting documentation, and having a thorough understanding of the client's business and industry rather than depending only on evidence supplied by management.

Targeted fraud risk mapping of susceptible areas, like payroll,

inventory, or procurement, should be a part of audit planning. Anomalies should be found using forensic investigation techniques (Odeyemi et al., 2024). In this process, data analytics is essential because it enables full-population testing instead of conventional sampling techniques (Handoko et al., 2020). This makes it possible for auditors to examine whole transaction populations and find anomalies. Particularly, methods like outlier detection and Benford's Law are employed to identify fraudulent activity in financial data and highlight unusual patterns. Even though technology greatly facilitates the detection of fraud, professional judgement and human interpretation are still essential for deciphering complex situations and reaching tenable conclusions (Brewster et al., 2021).

The importance of the forensic lens is further supported by recent empirical data. Adoption of forensic analytics has been linked in several jurisdictions between 2020 and 2024 to a decrease in average detection time (from 45 to 25 days) and an increase in fraud detection success rates (from 68% to 88%) (ResearchGate, 2025). A 2023 ICAB study conducted in Bangladesh discovered a statistically significant positive correlation between the detection of white-collar crimes and forensic accounting skills (ICAB, 2023). Furthermore, to

highlight the extent of fraud and the necessity of forensic methods, Bangladesh's central bank hired Big Four audit firms to examine losses totalling USD 17 billion in domestic banks (Reuters, 2025). Enormous fraud scandals in Bangladesh—such as over BDT 900 billion diverted via proxy accounts in banking (Corruption in Bangladesh, 2025)—underscore that forensic auditing is not optional but essential.

Investigative interviews delve deeper: auditors evaluate responses that differ, departmental inconsistencies, or indications of collusion (Enoayuk, 2013). Instead of using strict checklists, forensic accounting investigations frequently favour more flexible, interactive methods that involve staff members directly. It is still difficult to identify deliberate misrepresentations in these kinds of interviews (Lee & Welker, 2007). Beyond checklists, forensic auditing documentation emphasises narrative reasoning, red flags, evidence linkage, and logic chains that bolster conclusions, creating a convincing trail for further examination.

Additionally, using unpredictability (changing audit teams, surprise inspections, and different verification schedules) lowers the possibility that suspects will manipulate the process and helps discourage manipulation (Makofske, 2019).

In the end, using a forensic lens turns auditing into investigative assurance, bolstering external audit validity and improving management accountability, thus strengthening corporate governance.

This all-encompassing strategy is necessary to combat fraud, find hidden financial irregularities, and rebuild confidence in systems that far too frequently rely on conjecture rather than validation (Bhasin, 2015).

Case Studies of Data Analytics in Fraud Investigation

From paper-era deceit to digital-age manipulation, corporate fraud has flourished in Bangladesh, where informal practices, collusion, and poor governance frequently pass off financial misconduct as normal business operations. The most notorious example is still the

Destiny Group case. The group carried out one of the biggest Ponzi-style scams in South Asia through Destiny 2000, Destiny Tree Plantation, and several sister companies. Investigators estimate that over Tk 41,800 million (approximately Tk 4,118 crore) was embezzled from over 800,000 investors over the course of ten years, with roughly Tk 960 million laundered overseas (Prothom Alo, 2020). Additionally, the investigation conducted by Bangladesh Bank uncovered Tk 7.09 billion in commission payments that had been embezzled, as well as money that had been syphoned through money laundering channels in related entities (Financial Express, 2025; The Financial Express, 2025). Destiny's reported assets increased 358.8% in less than two years, from Tk 10.76 billion in June 2010 to Tk 26.19 billion in

March 2012, indicating systemic value inflation and misreporting (Financial Express, 2025). The astounding scope of the fraud was highlighted in January 2025 when a Dhaka court sentenced Lt Gen (retired) Harun-Ar-Rashid and Rafiqul Amin (Managing Director) to 12 years in prison and fined them Tk 4,515.57 crore for embezzlement (Telegraph / PTI, 2025).

The Evaly case illustrates how fraud has spread online. Evaly claimed to have over 3.5 million registered users and a monthly transaction volume of Tk 3 billion at its height (Prothom Alo, 2020). While the platform's declared assets were only Tk 1.21 billion, or just 22.3 percent of its liabilities, it acknowledged that as of mid-2021, it owed customers Tk 3.11 billion (The Financial Express, 2021). Despite this discrepancy, Evaly kept taking advance payments and transferring money to insider accounts while pretending that the transactions were legal until corrective action was taken (The Daily Star, 2022; Dhaka Tribune, 2021). Because of its incentives (such as cashback and discounts of up to 100-150 percent) and dependence on new inflows to cover existing obligations, analysts have dubbed the model a "retail Ponzi" (Dhaka Tribune, 2021). After the government and forensic audits revealed the financial gaps and inventory mismatch, the company collapsed.

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The Crescent Group scandal in trade finance revealed how state banks were depleted by manipulated letters of credit, phantom shipments, and fabricated export documents. Forged export invoices, collusion with banking authorities, and illegal money transfers overseas through Janata Bank were all part of the well-known scandal. According to a study, fake export documents were used to steal billions of taka, causing significant harm to Bangladesh's reputation and trade finance (Ullah, 2025). According to reports, Crescent borrowed more than Tk 51.3 billion from Janata Bank across several branches, and there were at least Tk 10.75 billion in claims of falsified paperwork and export overstatements (Prothom Alo / Prothom Alo English, 2018). Significant regulatory scrutiny and changes to export verification and letter of credit processes were brought about by the case (Prothom Alo, 2018; ResearchGate, 2025).

The changing fraud landscape is further demonstrated by other instances of corporate misreporting. In the Aftab Automobiles case, stakeholders were misled by inflated inventory and overstated revenues; after inconsistencies were discovered during audit and tax reviews, regulatory action was taken (local media, 2024). The severe repercussions of corruption in medical

emergencies were made evident by the Regent Hospital COVID-19 scam, which resulted in arrests, hospital suspensions, and widespread indignation due to phoney COVID test results, fraudulent billing to government programs, and illicit enrichment (Orubu et al., 2021). In the meantime, the Youth Development Multipurpose Cooperative Society used circular transfers between insider accounts and inflated return promises to defraud rural savers out of more than Tk 1,200 crore (local investigative reports, 2023). Even more scandalous, the PK Halder case (Prashanta Kumar Halder) was one of the biggest financial frauds in Bangladesh's history, involving the alleged embezzlement of over Tk 102 billion (USD ~ 854 million) across financial institutions (Wikipedia, 2025).

When taken as a whole, these cases show how fraud in Bangladesh adjusts to the various channels that are available, such as fake export invoices, inflated ledgers, online distractions, insider transfers, or fraudulent cooperative schemes. The schemes take advantage of foreseeable structural flaws in governance, regulatory gaps, informality's cultural acceptance, and oversight. Over the past ten years, the total losses from banking fraud alone (across several scandals) are estimated to have reached tens of thousands of crore taka,

severely damaging bank balance sheets and eroding public confidence (Prothom Alo / The Daily Star reports on various banking scandals).

These illustrations demonstrate the need for contemporary auditors to embrace a forensic mindset, which combines scepticism, data analytics, pattern recognition, and independent verification in order to uncover hidden connections, link intent to proof, and bolster public trust in corporate responsibility. When viewed through a forensic lens, auditors examine the motivations, patterns, and reasoning behind documents rather than just accepting them. They use methods like Benford's Law and outlier detection, test entire transaction populations (as opposed to sampling), conduct ratio and trend analyses over long time periods, and combine network and cash flow analyses to identify questionable connections or transaction clusters.

Forensic auditors also need to gather intelligence by connecting bank records, ownership structures, cross-entity flows, and cross-border transfers; questioning narrative explanations; using investigative interviewing; and cross-referencing independent third-party data (such as customs, shipping, tax, and bank confirmations). The auditor's reasoning, warning

signs, alternate theories, and the logic chains that connect the evidence to conclusions must all be documented in addition to the checklist procedures. Unpredictability is advantageous to audit plans because it allows for sampling patterns, surprise verifications, rotating teams, and different timing.

Crucially, using forensic viewpoints enhances standard auditing rather than takes its place. The forensic approach promotes auditor independence and resilience against bias or collusion in situations like Bangladesh, where there are informal controls, hierarchical pressure, regulatory gaps, inadequate investor protection, and possible control overrides. In settings where assumptions predominate and oversight is

frequently incomplete, it aids in re-establishing equilibrium.

All things considered, the development of fraud in Bangladesh—from Destiny to Evaly to banking scandals and cooperative swindles—demonstrates the financial crime industry's tenacious adaptability. Modern auditing needs to transform into investigative assurance in order to see through the illusions. Auditors need to be more than just number-checkers; they need to be detectives. It is now essential to uphold trust, safeguard stakeholders, and facilitate meaningful governance in Bangladesh's corporate and financial sectors to adopt a forensic mindset, which is based on scepticism, evidence triangulation, analytics, and narrative reasoning.

Challenges and Opportunities

In Bangladesh, forensic auditing and fraud detection are at a critical point. On the one hand, there is a business environment that is rapidly digitising. This environment promises growth, but it also exposes the system to cybersecurity threats, weak enforcement, and fraudulent transactions (Chowdhury, 2025). On the other side is a deeply ingrained informal culture, which is typified by unregulated activities like Hundi, along with inadequate governance and a dearth of investigative tools. Both the difficulties and the possibilities of Bangladesh's forensic audit environment are defined by the junction of modernisation and informality, where criminal tactics advance more quickly than legal remedies.

Weak corporate governance and a brittle ethical culture are the root causes of the first significant issue. In contrast to institutional accountability, family ownership and personality-driven management frequently dominate governance practices, which are still in their infancy. The presence of "independent directors" has not yet resulted in significant oversight, and boards and audit committees usually lack independence. Focused control promotes form over-substance compliance and permits management overrides. Overlapping jurisdictions,

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political meddling, and procedural inertia impede justice and undermine deterrence, even when regulatory organisations like the ACC, Bangladesh Bank, or the BSEC try to step in. Trust in enforcement mechanisms is further undermined by the continued low litigation risk and inadequate investor protection.

Limited technical capacity is the second obstacle. Bangladesh consistently produces chartered accountants, but only a small percentage of them have received forensic methodology training, which reflects the lack of knowledge about forensic accounting in developing nations (Efiang, 2012). There are gaps in regulation and education because forensic work is multidisciplinary, encompassing data science, accounting, and law. As a result, manual checking is frequently used in investigations instead of digital evidence analysis. Financial records are scattered across manual registers, separate ERP modules, or unstandardised ledgers, which exacerbates the issue of data fragmentation. Traceability is hampered by the lack of data integration across agencies, and forensic tools' analytical capabilities are weakened by paper-based processes.

These structural flaws are exacerbated by cultural resistance. Instead of providing protection, fraud examination is frequently misunderstood as

distrust. Because management discourages thorough audits to "avoid scandal" and employees fear retaliation, whistleblowers are silenced and isolated (Farooqi et al., 2017). Early warnings are not reported in the absence of strong whistleblower protection (Ningsih et al., 2024). New threats include payment diversion, data tampering, and cyber manipulation. Digital forensics is an urgent skill gap since auditors trained under traditional frameworks frequently lack the IT literacy necessary to identify malware-based fraud or ERP overrides.

However, these difficulties open up new possibilities. Massive data trails created by the growth of ERP platforms and digital payments enable auditors to perform continuous monitoring and full-population testing (Sun et al., 2023). Real-time anomaly detection, pattern recognition, and predictive fraud risk modelling are now made possible by artificial intelligence and big data analytics. AI is incredibly useful for proactive auditing because of its ability to adjust to changing schemes. A new generation of professionals who are proficient in both accounting and analytics is being produced by professional organisations such as the ACFE Bangladesh Chapter and the ICAB, which are creating specialised training in forensic and cyber auditing.

Modernisation of regulations is also in progress. The BSEC's digital surveillance tools target capital-market manipulation, while Bangladesh Bank's FIU now connects suspicious transaction data with tax and customs systems. Listed businesses increasingly view compliance as a strategic advantage as a result of investor and ESG scrutiny. The audit ecosystem in Bangladesh is moving from reactive detection to predictive prevention as a result of AI-driven workflows that increase audit coverage and transparency.

In the end, legacy flaws like fragmented data, sluggish enforcement, and inadequate governance continue to be significant (Rashid, 2011). However, a shift is being marked by increasing regulatory cooperation, digital traceability, and an accountable culture. The issue is not whether fraud can be eliminated—it cannot—but rather whether auditors, regulators, and business executives can outsmart the scammers. Bangladesh has the chance to rethink integrity and establish forensic auditing as a cornerstone of sustainable governance in the digital era during that race.

Conclusion

In Bangladesh, auditing is about to enter a pivotal period where investigative vigilance and financial verification are merging. Traditional audits that

only looked at accuracy are no longer adequate, as evidenced by the rise in corporate frauds, which range from trade-based money laundering to digital Ponzi schemes. These days, maintaining credibility and capital requires a forensic mindset that is analytical, sceptical, and evidence-based. Beyond just identifying criminal activity, forensic auditing also interprets intent, links data to behaviour, and turns compliance into proactive risk mitigation. Courage, technical proficiency, and cooperation between auditors, management, regulators, and law enforcement are all necessary for this transition. Transparency must be promoted, whistleblowers must be empowered, and scrutiny must be seen as an investment rather than an intrusion. Current scandals like Evaly, Destiny, and Crescent highlight serious problems with governance while also signalling a sea change. As ethics and analytics come together, auditors can become more than just record-keepers; they can become architects of trust, making sure that every balance sheet shows honesty rather than deception.

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Understanding IFRS 18

A New Era in the Presentation of Financial Statements

Md. Atiqur Rahaman FCA

The Author is a
Fellow Member, ICAB and
Financial Controller
Runner Automobiles PLC

The article was reviewed by
Mahbub Ahmed Siddique FCA

IFRS 18, named "Presentation and Disclosure in Financial Statements," was formally released by the IASB on April 9, 2024. This standard is a result of the IASB's initiatives on the Primary Financial Statements project, responding to the increasing requests from investors for more detailed information about companies' financial performance. Its main objective is to enhance the clarity of financial information in statements, thus offering investors a stronger basis for evaluating and contrasting corporate performance.

The New Requirements for IFRS 18

The implementation of IFRS 18 introduces three essential categories of requirements designed to enhance the comparability, transparency, and usefulness of financial information:

Structured Profit or Loss Statement

The initial requirement establishes a systematic method for presenting the statement of profit or loss, necessitating the inclusion of two newly defined subtotals: Operating Profit and Profit Before Financing and Tax. This framework will provide a uniform foundation for investors' analyses and improve the comparability of financial performance among companies.

Management-Defined Performance Measures (MPMs)

Entities must disclose specific performance measures defined by management, which illustrate how management oversees and conveys the financial performance of the entity. This enhances transparency and offers insight into the metrics utilized internally by management.

Improved Guidance on Aggregation and Disaggregation

The third requirement enhances the guidance related to the grouping of information, ensuring that investors receive material information and that financial statements are more understandable and useful.

The incorporation of categories and supplementary subtotals in the profit or loss statement addresses investors' apprehensions about the difficulties in comparing financial performance among companies, given that the structure and content of these statements have traditionally differed. Importantly, Operating Profit, a commonly utilized performance metric, has not been defined in IFRS Accounting Standards until this point, resulting in inconsistencies in its application.

Understanding IFRS 18

A New Era in the Presentation of Financial Statements

Pillars	What It Means	Key Impact
Structured Income Statement	Mandates three new defined subtotals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Operating (core business) • Investing (assets/investments) • Financing (capital & debt) 	Allow investors to instantly isolate and compare core operating profitability.
Management Performance Measures (MPMs)	Strict rules for non-GAAP metrics: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Must be reconciled to IFRS numbers. • Disclosed in a single, dedicated note. • Explanation of why they are useful. 	Tames "alternative" metrics, reducing clutter and potential for misleading information.
Enhanced Cash Flow Disclosures	More granular disclosure requirements for the components of operating cash flows.	Provides a clearer view of cash timing and drivers from receivables, payables, and other expenses.

Categories in the Statement of Profit or Loss

IFRS 18 establishes three new categories aimed at standardizing the format of the statement of profit or loss:

Operating

This is the standard category that includes all items which do not meet the criteria for classification under the investing or financing categories.

Investing

This category generally comprises income and expenses associated with investments that are accounted for using the equity method, in addition to returns from cash equivalents and various other investments.

Financing

This category encompasses income and expenses related to

liabilities that are exclusively tied to financing activities, including interest expenses and the impacts of fluctuations in interest rates.

The operational category is intended to record income and expenses arising from the entity's primary business operations, functioning as a residual category for all items that do not fit into other classifications, regardless of whether they are volatile or atypical.

Essential Subtotals for Evaluating Performance

The standard additionally presents two new subtotals: Operating Profit and Profit Before Financing and Income Tax. These subtotals aim to enhance the analysis of financial performance among companies. The Operating Profit subtotal offers a pertinent depiction of an entity's operations, whereas Profit Before Financing and Income

Tax enables users to assess performance prior to the effects of financing choices.

Understanding Management-Defined Performance Measures (MPMs)

IFRS 18 characterizes MPMs as income and expense subtotals that are not defined by IFRS Accounting Standards, which are disclosed in public communications outside of financial statements. MPMs convey management's viewpoint on particular elements of the entity's financial performance.

MPMs are extracted from the statement of profit or loss and signify a limited set of performance metrics that can be employed in performance communication, including adjusted profit or loss, adjusted operating profit, or adjusted EBITDA. The standard specifies that subtotals mandated by IFRS are not classified as MPMs and provides explicit examples of what constitutes non-MPMs.

For each MPM, entities must disclose:

- Clarifications regarding the usefulness of the MPM in conveying financial performance information.
- The methodology employed for calculating the MPM.
- A comparison between the MPM and the closest IFRS-defined subtotal.
- The effects of income tax and the implications for non-controlling interests for each element in the reconciliation.
- Any modifications to MPMs should be elucidated, and comparative data must be adjusted accordingly.

- MPMs are now disclosed in the financial statements in a transparent way, **explained and reconciled and subject to audit**
- All information about MPMs is required to **be disclosed in a single note**
- Under IFRS 18, public communications include- Management Commentary, Press release, Investor presentations - **In contrast, oral communications and social media posts are outside the ambit of it.**
- MPMs are now part of the audited financial statements, and **the auditor will need to assess the completeness of MPMs** and obtain from management an understanding of how they are identified from period to period

Understanding IFRS 18

A New Era in the Presentation of Financial Statements

IFRS 18: Revised requirement for IAS 7

Requirements of IAS 7	Current Requirements	Requirements of IFRS 18
Starting point of operating cashflows in the statement of cash flow when indirect method is Used	Profit or Loss before tax	Operating Profit or Loss
Classification of interest and dividend cash inflows	Accounting Policy Choice: Operating or investing	No accounting policy choice Investing cash flows except for entities with specified main business activities (Bank, insurance, investment entity)
Classification of Interest cash outflow	Accounting Policy Choice: Operating or Financing cash flows	No accounting policy choice Financing cash flows, except for entities with specified main business activities
Classification of dividend outflows	Accounting policy choice: operating or financing cash flows	No accounting policy choice Financing cash flows

Other Changes

Goodwill (IAS 38)

- to be presented as a line item in the Balance Sheet

Additional Earnings Per Share (IAS 33)

- In addition to existing EPS (Basic & Diluted EPS) as per IAS 33, an entity is permitted to disclose additional amounts per share such as EBITDA per share, OPDAI per share

Interim Financial Reporting (IAS 34)

- Amended to conform to IFRS 18 for annual financial statements

Transition to IFRS 18

- Apply IFRS 18 retrospectively in accordance with IAS 8 – Basis of preparation of financial statements

IFRS 18 - Effect on financial statements

IFRS 18 affects the complete set of financial statements, including:

Revised Criteria for the Collection and Separation of Data

The updated requirements concerning aggregation and disaggregation are designed to improve the guidance for organizing information, which includes the presentation and disclosure of operating expenses. IFRS 18 offers direction on how to decide if information should be included in primary financial statements or disclosed in the notes. Companies are encouraged to provide structured summaries of income, expenses, assets, liabilities, equity, and cash flows within primary financial statements, while also revealing

additional significant information in the notes.

Entities are required to label and describe items in a way that accurately represents their characteristics. The use of vague labels such as "other" should be avoided unless no more descriptive label can be identified.

Effective Dates and Adoption Guidelines for IFRS 18

IFRS 18 will come into effect for annual reporting periods starting on or after January 1, 2027. These standard mandates retrospective application, which requires a reconciliation

between the profit or loss statement prepared under IAS 1 and the one presented in compliance with IFRS 18.

Entities may choose to adopt IFRS 18 early, facilitating enhanced financial reporting practices.

IFRS 18 is anticipated to greatly improve the presentation and disclosure of financial information, allowing investors to analyze and compare the performance of companies more efficiently.

Understanding IFRS 18

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A Sample PnL

Statement of Profit & Loss (IFRS 18 Format)		
For the year ended 31 December 20XX		
Operating	Revenue	1,000,000
	Cost of goods sold	(700,000)
	Gross profit	300,000
	Selling and distribution expenses	(80,000)
	Administrative expenses	(70,000)
	Research and development expenses	(20,000)
	Other operating income	15,000
	Other operating expenses	(10,000)
	Operating profit	135,000
	Investing	Share of profit from associates
Dividend income		3,000
Interest income (investments)		5,000
Gain on disposal of investments		4,000
Loss on disposal of investments		(2,000)
Total investing income/ (expense)		22,000
Profits before financing and income tax	179,000	
Financing	Interest expense (on loans)	(30,000)
	Interest expense (on lease liabilities)	(5,000)
	Other financing costs	(2,000)
	Total financing expense	(37,000)
Profit before income tax	105,000	
Income Tax	Income tax expense	(50,000)
	Profit from continuing operations	55,000
Discontinued Operation	Profit from discontinued operations	-
	Net profit	55,000
Required Subtotals		Mandatory
Additional Subtotals		Additional

Readiness for Implementation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the Accounting Sector of Bangladesh

ABM Fuad Hassan ACA¹ | Dr. Mofijul Hoq Masum FCMA²

The Authors are:

¹Associate Member, ICAB

²Associate Professor
United International University

The article was reviewed by
K Atique-e-Rabbani FCA

Abstract

The world is rapidly advancing alongside technological innovation, with Artificial Intelligence (AI) playing a key role in transforming business processes, including accounting and healthcare. This paper explores the readiness of Bangladeshi organizations to adopt AI in accounting and finance. A quantitative methodology was used, employing a digital survey (via Google Forms) shared with professionals through networks. The survey was based on the Digital Readiness Level 4.0 model (Pirola et al., 2019), covering five dimensions: People, Process, Strategy, Technology, and Integration. Findings highlight strengths such as strong IT security, data backup, ERP usage, and departmental collaboration. Weaknesses include poor internal communication, outdated cloud systems, reluctance to adopt new technologies, and limited AI awareness. Additional challenges include cybersecurity risks, lack of unified AI goals, limited data transparency, and potential job displacement due to automation. Addressing these issues is essential to prepare Bangladeshi organizations for effective AI integration in accounting and finance.

Keywords

Artificial Intelligence, Blockchain, Cloud storage, Machine Learning, Big Data

Introduction

Background of the Study

The rapid advancement of technology, especially Artificial Intelligence (AI), has transformed various fields, notably accounting. AI is widely used for automation, decision support, and data analysis, offering a competitive edge to companies. Its rise is driven by big data, complex infrastructures, and advanced technologies like blockchain, machine learning, neural networks, deep learning, and natural language processing (NLP), enabling real-time data analysis and strategic insights. Globally, AI tools such as RPA and NLP are reshaping roles in accounting by enhancing accuracy and efficiency. While Bangladesh has seen economic and accounting sector growth, it lags in AI implementation. Immediate adoption is crucial for operational efficiency, reduced resource use, and increased profitability. However, concerns remain over whether current organizational infrastructures can support a smooth transition. Without a strong foundation, AI adoption may lead to resource loss. Vendors and organizations must assess readiness before implementing AI systems to

Readiness for Implementation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the Accounting Sector of Bangladesh

ensure successful integration and sustainable outcomes.

Objectives of the Study

This study assesses the readiness of Bangladesh's accounting sector for AI adoption, aiming to ensure a smooth transition to a technology-driven future. The project focuses on:

- The application of AI and related technologies in business practices
- The organizational structure needed for effective AI implementation
- A quantitative, objective analysis through a countrywide survey of accounting professionals in Bangladesh to measure AI readiness

Definition of Key Terms

Artificial Intelligence is a mix of software and equipment as a substitute for human intelligence that enables us to solve complex problems using reasoning, learning, elucidating, and recognizing patterns same as human experts. Artificial Intelligence uses expert systems instead of expert human and apply machine intelligence instead of human intelligence. Artificial Intelligence has a great impact on helping managers in making decisions by reducing repetitive decisions, providing more precise information, simplifying complex decision factors, and fact processing in data analysis (Askary, Abu-Ghazaleh & Tahat, 2018). Fact processing in data analysis is the process of transforming raw data into verified and

structured facts for interpretation and decision-making.

Review of the Literature

Literature Survey (Artificial Intelligence & Modern Business)

Kumar et al. (2022) conducted research to characterize the applications and benefits of integrated AI and blockchain platforms across different verticals of business using a bibliometric analysis. The study conducted also unveils the uses of AI and block chain capabilities in organizations globally. A list of numerous capabilities of AI, block chain, Big Data and machine learning have been studied in detail and the real-life examples of those are summarized below:

1. E Commerce

- Platform for Ecommerce operationalization:** The websites for ecommerce structures can be optimized through the incorporation of Artificial Intelligence and Blockchain technologies, through which using blockchain the cross border electronic payment problem is solved, whereas the online decision making can also be facilitated using the recommender system which uses the machine learning algorithm. An example of such can be observed in the operation of Alibaba.

2. Finance and Accounting

- a. **Insurance system:** With the help of machine learning algorithm (XGBoost) and framework based on blockchain the insurance system can detect fraudulent and fake claims, data about dodgy customers and reduce the overall monetary losses from insurance industry. For instance, automation have been used by Lemonade Insurance. They use AI based bots to underwrite policies and maintain claims within fraction of seconds.
- b. **Evaluation of Credit:** Blockchain and deep machine learning networks and models can assist in delivering credible information about transactions and evaluating credit performance of customers.
- c. **Portfolio optimization:** Automatic audit process

may be initiated with the help of Blockchain and Neural network which can secure settlement process.

- d. **FinBrain:** It is a smart finance system that incorporates Big Data, AI and cloud computing with finance to enable computerized and secure financial dealings.
- e. **Prevention of Corporate Frauds:** By integrating Blockchain, AI and smart contract financial audits can be automated and internal deficiencies of audit can be highlighted to prevent corporate frauds caused by auditors' mistake.

3. Healthcare

- a. **Clinical Practices:** A generalizable predictive system that runs based on AI can help curb pandemic and epidemic risk and thereby help to safeguard public health. An example is

BlueDot. It is a Canadian startup that uses Natural language processing to identify early signs of COVID-19 spread in Wuhan before official announcement.

- b. **GuardHealth:** A platform using blockchain, smart contract and trust model incorporated using graph neural network which acts as a preserving and sharing system for sensitive information.

4. Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)

- a. **IPR Management:** IPR lifecycle can be managed through the use of AI and IPR assets can be notarized using technologies based on blockchain. Machine learning can also be used to compare and contrast IPR assets. Such as IPwe which provides registry of IP assets including patents based on blockchain. With the help of AI, market value, rights and comparison among competitors can be thoroughly analyzed. It also provides a secured medium for analytics of licensing, monetization and litigation and enables notarization.

5. Management

- a. **Corporate Governance:** Aragon use blockchain and smart contract to allow companies have computerized governance. Shareholders can easily

Readiness for Implementation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in the Accounting Sector of Bangladesh

vote on decisions with the help of AI and also manage proposals and quorum. This improves transparency, reduces costs and increase accountability of the management.

6. Marketing

a. Customer Service: Customer interaction can be meticulously managed using autonomous AI agents in Fetch.ai. It combines data from blockchain and IoT to answer FAQs, appointment booking and recommendation of product securely without the help of third-party platforms.

7. Smart Manufacturing

a. Cyber Production System: Siemen’s MindSphere links IoT with equipment’s for manufacturing and uses AI for predictive analytics and detecting anomalies in production. With the help of blockchain the traceability of each product component can be ensured which increases quality assurance and reduces the risk of faulty production.

8. Social Media

a. Controlling Spread of False Messages: Startups like TruStory has attempted to authenticate shared information by assigning tokens based on validation of peer.

b. Secure Instant Messaging: Status.im is a decentralized messaging platform that uses blockchain for encryption and anonymity and AI for spam detection and monitoring behavior patterns on the web.

9. Supply Chain

a. Smart Farming: Satellite data along with AI weather forecast information is used by IBM for enabling smart farming. Moreover, blockchain is used for farm traceability. Soil, water and raw inventory levels can be monitored in real-time by Edge computing.

10. Transportation

a. Automation in Airports: SITA uses blockchain powered by predictive analytics to create a smooth customer experience. Through biometric boarding, secure ID verification and personalized travel appointments based on AI it helps reduce time consumption and efficiency.

Research Methods

Research Design

The survey follows a digital readiness level 4.0 model as proposed by studies performed in 2019 by Pirola, et.al. A digital survey form is prepared in Google Forms with the necessary questions and individuals are asked to fill up

and send back their response. The survey questions measure perceived readiness across the following domains:

- People
- Strategy
- Process
- Technology
- Integration

Sample

The sample size was approximately 44 respondents. A cross-sectional survey was conducted to collect data from practicing accounting professionals across different regions and sectors in Bangladesh. The respondents mostly included professionals working in the accounting or finance function and involved with the top management of the organizations. The respondents were contacted via professional networks at our disposal which were mainly whatsapp groups dedicated for ICAB/ICMAB and Facebook pages. The have sent their responses though google form.

Questionnaire Development

The survey questions are given below:

Questions:

Demographic questions:

1. Please specify your gender
2. What is your age?

3. Which industry are you currently working in?
4. What is your salary range?
5. Service experience

Dimension 1: People

1. Employees are willing to implement AI in their regular accounting tasks.
2. There are ample training opportunities for staff development.
3. Accounting staff understand AI concepts and ethics.
4. Our management is comfortable with our clearly defined job roles.

Dimension 2: Strategy

1. Our strategic goals are communicated effectively throughout the organization.
2. Our strategy is consistent with recent changes supporting the implementation of AI.
3. Management sees the use of AI & analytics in finance as a competitive advantage.
4. Our organization strategies support innovation of IT based tools. (Such as AI, automation and data analytics).

Dimension 3: Process

1. Our business processes are well documented with audit

trails, logs and changes recorded.

2. A standard operating procedure is maintained, which is clearly communicated.
3. We have previously used tools to support process automation.
4. We have identified repetitive tasks which could be suitable for AI/automation.

Dimension 4: Technology

1. Our organization uses up-to-date technology with cloud-based support.
2. Data security is a top priority.
3. Our systems are integrated across departments (cross functional integration).
4. Our data has proper backed up measures and is stored securely.

Dimension 5: Integration

1. Our departments collaborate on shared goals.
2. We use EPR or similar platforms to support organizational integration.
3. There is a strong alignment between HR, Accounting, Finance and operations.
4. Our internal communications are strong, which can support digital collaboration.

Data Collection and analysis

A purposive sampling technique is used in this study. We tried to seek a wide variety of individuals to ensure an all-inclusiveness throughout our study. The questionnaire included a mix of open-ended questions and Likert scale items based on authenticated AI readiness indicators from existing frameworks and popular research. Descriptive statistics will be used to summarize the survey responses. A thorough investigation will be made of the responses to unveil the difficulties in incorporating AI. The scores ranged from 1-5, with 1 being the lowest score and 5 being the highest score. The scores denoted the following:

1="Very Weak", 2="Weak", 3="Neutral", 4="Strong", 5="Very Strong"

Research Findings & Analysis

The existent data collection method, nevertheless, resulted in the collection of 44 surveys using an online questionnaire sent via Google Forms. To improve response rates and reduce partial responses, controls were incorporated such as making all questions compulsory and employing respondent friendly terminology for the Likert scale questions so that the form could be easily approachable and fully completed.

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The results are summarized, and discussions are presented in a systematic manner below:

Figure 1: Gender of the respondents

Please specify your gender

44 responses

From the above chart we can observe that among the total respondents 9.1% (4 respondents) were female and 90.9% (40 respondents) were male. This somewhat indicates in a rough manner the dominance of male respondents in the top management of different companies across Bangladesh.

Figure 2: Age of the respondents

What is your age?

44 responses

The above chart describes the age range of the respondents. It can be observed that the age range with the highest count is 35 to 45 years, which is 52.3% (23 respondents). Second comes the age range of 25 to 35 years, which is 40.9% (18 respondents). Thereafter the age range of below 25 years which has 4.5% (2 respondents) and the least percentage within the age range of 55 and above which is 2.3% (1 respondent). This indicates the majority of the respondents involved in the top management are around 35 to 45 years.

Figure 3: Industry of the repondents

Which industry are you currently working in?

44 responses

From the above chart it has been observed that the respondents belong from different sectors with the highest number of respondents from the service industry which is 38.6% (17 respondents) and 13.6% (6 respondents) from auditing, 11.4% (5 respondents) from RMG/textile/accessories industry and 9.1% (4 respondents) from banking industry.

Figure 4: Income of the respondents

What is your salary / income range?

44 responses

The above chart shows that the respondents had different ranges of income. The highest count was obtained from the range BDT 50,000 to BDT 100,000 which was about 40.9% (18 respondents). Thereafter, the range BDT 100,000 to BDT 150,000 which was about 25% (11 respondents). The range above BDT 200,000 was about 13.6% (6 respondents). Range BDT 150,000 to BDT 200,000 had 11.4% (5 respondents). The least was the range of BDT 30,000 - 50,000 BDT having 9.1% (4 respondents).

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Figure 5: Experience of the respondents

Service experience
44 responses

The chart shows that number of years of experience of the respondents. The highest was above 10 years, having 40.9% (18 respondents). And the least was below 2 years of experience which was about 2.3% (1 respondent).

Response Findings

The results are discussed below:

Dimension 1: People (Average score 3.75, Strong)

Dimension 1: People indicate individual readiness and their knowledge, attitudes, interaction, and administration regarding the integration of Artificial Intelligence within their routine tasks. The average score received in this dimension was 3.75, which implies that the respondents’ perceptions were strong regarding the preparedness of human resources in this regard.

The respondents agreed that the employees were willing to implement the AI tools and capabilities into their daily

routing to derive their benefits. This shows high willingness and acceptance among employees, suggesting openness to technological shift. The respondents also agreed that there were training opportunities undertaken by the organizations for the employees relating to artificial intelligence and technology which suggests that the organization capitalizes in the technological changes and sponsors in increasing AI capabilities, which is an optimistic insight. The respondents also agreed that the accounting staff understand AI concepts and ethics which imply that employees are reasonably well-informed, diminishing risks connected with misapplication or concern of AI. However, the respondents

were neutral when it came to their management being comfortable with clearly defined job roles on AI. This indicates some vagueness in job functions associated with AI or resistance from their management.

While the staff are eager and skilled, there’s still a requirement for improvement in communication and transparency of roles within the employees and management. This could potentially decelerate AI implementation in spite of progressive staff readiness.

Dimension 2: Strategy (Average score 3.50, Slightly strong)

Dimension 2: Strategy evaluates how well the administrative policy promotes AI initiatives.

The average score received in this dimension was 3.50, which indicates that the respondents' perception was slightly strong about the organizational policies regarding AI implementation.

The respondents replied with neutrality when it comes to their strategic goals on AI being communicated effectively throughout the organization. This unveils a weak spot within the organization indicating that there are communication gaps with may hamper the arrangement and employee morale. Moreover, the respondents agreed that the management sees AI in finance as a competitive advantage. This implies that there is a strong managerial viewpoint on the benefits of AI in finance, a serious factor for its adoption.

The respondents also agreed that their organizational strategies support innovation of IT tools signaling a wider openness to digital transformation. Despite all these the respondents are neutral about whether their existing strategy is consistent with recent AI-supportive changes suggesting strategic orientation with AI is only mild, indicating a clear need for the revision of the current strategic roadmap to align with the dynamic AI related changes.

It can be said that there is a robust strategic footing, particularly in terms of management attitude and documentation processes. However, the strategic acclimatization to recent AI trends is not yet fully developed (having scored 3), which seems

like a small hinderance to optimal implementation of AI in accounting and finance.

Dimension 3: Process (Average score 3.75, Strong)

Dimension 3: Process appraises the development of internal processes and practices to adapt and integrate AI within the system. The average score received in this dimension was 3.75, which indicates that the respondents' perception regarding the internal processes were relatively strong in comparison to the other two dimensions discussed above.

The respondents agreed that their business processes are well documented with logs and audit trails. This shows that there are strong documentation practices which assist traceability, which is essential for AI implementation. The respondents also agreed that their organizations instill standard operating procedures which are maintained and communicated throughout the organization. This indicates that operational uniformity exists, permitting easier adoption of AI tools. The respondents agreed that the repetitive tasks within the organization which are suitable for implementation of AI have been identified. This indicates that it is a good

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foundation since identifying automation latency is crucial for AI readiness. Respondents have also responded with neutrality when it comes to the use of process automation tools previously within their organization. This indicates inadequate experience with automation which is a potential risk towards AI implementation.

It can be said that the processes within the organizations are well-aligned for AI, principally concerning repetitive task identification, information system security, and departmental integration, but technological infrastructure regarding cloud-based systems may be inadequate and with very limited experience with such AI capabilities.

Dimension 4: Technology (Average score 3.75, Strong)

Dimension 4: Process appraises the technological infrastructure within the organization and collaboration between information systems and the functional departments. The average score received in this dimension was 3.75, which is the high among the dimensions and indicates that the respondents' perception regarding the technological systems were strong.

Respondents have agreed that data security is a top priority within their organization, indicating sincere importance is being provided to security — vital for AI and analytics to prosper with sufficient credential. Respondents have

also agreed that the systems for information processing are integrated across departments. This shows that cross-functional integration promotes AI that is contingent on smooth data flow. However, respondents exhibited neutral response regarding whether their organizations use up-to-date cloud technology, this means cloud-based technologies may not always be up to date and hence IT infrastructures could be upgraded; cloud-readiness is important for scalability of AI tools within the organization's operation. The respondents agreed that the data from the information systems are backed up and stored securely maintaining backup procedures. This implies that strong data infrastructures are present within the organizations which is foundational for AI implementation.

Dimension 5: Integration (Average score 4.00, Strong)

Dimension 5: Integration appraises the structural integration within the organization and collaboration between information systems and the functional departments. The average score received in this dimension was 4.00, which is the highest among all the dimensions and indicates that the respondents' perception

regarding the integration of technological systems were the strongest in contrast to the other dimensions discussed above.

Respondents also agreed that internal departments within the organization collaborate and work together on shared goals which implies that a high inter-departmental collaboration exists which will promote AI association across several functions of the organization. The respondents agreed that their organizations have been using ERP or similar platforms to support accounting and finance functions which indicate technological integration and data control. Respondents agreed that there are alignments between Human Resource, Accounting, Finance, and Operations to streamline the processes within the

organization which signals that cross-functional synergy between the departments is high, assisting AI integration. Lastly, respondents also agreed that there is presence of strong internal communications for digital collaboration between the functional departments suggesting strong support for digital tools and communication within the organization.

Overall, technology is obviously a strong area since there is strong infrastructure, collaboration, and digital integration, placing the organization appropriately for AI adoption.

Strengths

From the analysis and the discussion above we can identify several aspects of the information technology infrastructure that are

commendable. These include:

- ❖ **Data security:** Data security is considered a priority within organizations. It is observed that most respondents have agreed to have a strong internal IT security to ensure proper transmission of data and prevent data leakage. This is very commendable since AI implementation often require handling sensitive data where data leakage can be very damaging to the organization's operation and reputation.
- ❖ **Data backup:** Data backup system is maintained. Respondents have also agreed that the data is properly maintained and backed up in a secured system which can be easily retrieved if a when required. In the rapidly changing environment and a heavily IT based atmosphere an accident can result in loss of crucial data from the system. To prevent such mishap from happening data backup is essential for companies' smooth operation.
- ❖ **Use of ERP:** Organizations usually have an ERP installed in their information system. This means a strong

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organizational atmosphere is already present which can help in promoting the deployment of AI technologies.

- ❖ **Collaboration:** The departments have strong internal communication for collaboration within the system. Moreover, departments have strong inter-functional integration to collaborate within HR, Accounting, Finance and Marketing.

Weaknesses

From the analysis and the discussion above we can identify several aspects of the information technology infrastructure that require alteration. These include:

- ❖ **Unclear roles regarding AI:** There happens to be some vagueness regarding AI related roles. Management should provide instantaneous attention regarding the uniform communication within the organization for having a strong foundation for AI implementation.
- ❖ **Recent changes not considered:** The recent trends on AI application may not be thoroughly considered by the

management. This could essentially lead to disruption of organizational processes if the changes within the business practices are not closely monitored for success.

- ❖ **AI concept is relatively new:** The organizations are yet to implement seamless AI integration into their system. Change management may be required for the initial implementation of AI tools within the system.
- ❖ **Outdated cloud technologies:** The organizations may not be running the updated cloud technologies to support their systems. The management of organizations should consider whether the technology and digital tools are up to date for instant implementation of AI. This was also highlighted by Kosaraju, D. (2024).

Other challenges

According to Gotthard et al. (2020), several critical challenges must be addressed before AI adoption:

- **Vulnerability and cybersecurity:** AI-powered financial systems are very

susceptible to cyberattacks, with hackers abusing studied behaviors to breach private data held by RPA.

- **Having the right strategy is crucial:** Abiding general industry trends may disregard business-specific needs, leading to unproductive RPA implementation where simpler solutions might serve better.
- **Transparency:** Management must impartially assess RPA operation, requiring integrity and openness to appraise its business impact.
- **Displacement of jobs:** As AI replaces routine accounting and auditing tasks (Chen et al., 2020), job displacement becomes a major concern. Without skill upgrades, workers risk becoming obsolete in a quickly evolving environment.

These arguments highlight the need for strategic planning, cybersecurity, transparency, and workforce reskilling in AI implementation.

Discussion

Conclusions

The global shift toward digitalization has led to

extensive AI and RPA adoption across sectors like finance and healthcare, enhancing efficiency and dropping costs. These technologies are now vital for business competitiveness and sustainability. In Bangladesh, while AI offers noteworthy benefits, challenges persist due to insufficient infrastructure and unfamiliarity. Effective adoption requires clear AI roles, nonstop tech updates, and effective change management to overcome resistance. AI remains underutilized in many Bangladeshi entities. Future research should explore accountants' dynamic roles, the use of new data, application challenges, and the effect of technological substitutions to guarantee smooth and safe incorporation of AI in organizations.

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Agreeing with the Boss

A Lesson in Balance, Culture and Communication

Sajedul Alam Mazumder ACA

The Author is an Associate Member, ICAB and Senior Manager Financial Planning & Reporting Edotco Bangladesh Co. Ltd.

In the professional world, one of the most less-talked yet critical skills is knowing how to deal with disagreement, especially when that disagreement involves your boss. It may seem like a simple choice - either you agree or you don't. But how we choose the right and diplomatic way to respond can significantly affect our credibility, relationships, and career growth.

We all want to be honest. We all value integrity and sound judgment. Yet we soon learn that honesty must be paired with the ability to express differing views without causing friction. In some environments, disagreement is seen as initiative provided it is

appreciated by the counterpart, otherwise, it is perceived as confrontation. Navigating this delicate balance is one of the key elements to professional maturity.

In a young Chartered Accountant's career, especially during articleship in a Chartered Accountancy (CA) firm, a different kind of culture often prevails. Audit firms tend to foster an environment where juniors are expected even to ask questions, challenge assumptions and contribute critically. The approach is always participative.

When an audit team reviews financial statements or internal controls, every layer of scrutiny matters. A junior associate

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raising a red flag or presenting an alternative viewpoint is not only welcomed but also appreciated. This critical approach enhances audit quality and promotes professional skepticism, one of the fundamental principles of auditing. Obviously, this largely depends on the mindset of the boss and it varies person to person.

The shift from public accounting to corporate life often brings a surprising cultural adjustment. Unlike the audit environment where robust debates are routine, corporate organizations are typically more structured and hierarchical. Communication tends to be more controlled, and decisions are often made by consensus or by authority.

In such an environment, expressing disagreement, particularly in group meetings or public forums, can be perceived as resistance. Employees may feel pressure to align with the boss's opinion, regardless of personal reservations. Silence is seen as professionalism, while open disagreement, however polite, may be viewed as a challenge to authority.

This doesn't mean that people lose their judgment or turn into "yes-men." Rather, they learn that timing, tone and context matter more than the opinion itself. Professionals in corporate settings often learn to express concerns in subtle ways, perhaps through a private conversation after the meeting or through a carefully worded email suggesting reconsideration.

This adjustment is not easy for those coming from an audit background. It can feel unnatural or even dishonest to hold back an opinion. But the reality is that every organization has its own communication rhythm, and learning that rhythm is a vital part of fitting in and being effective. Of course, corporate culture and tone of the top is very important and play a crucial role in this regard.

So, how do we manage disagreement when speaking up might risk friction and staying silent might compromise our integrity?

One answer lies in the idea of "agreeing to disagree" not in a dismissive way, but in a respectful, strategic manner. It means accepting a difference of opinion without letting it become personal or disruptive. It means recognizing that sometimes, maintaining the relationship or supporting the broader team objective is more important than winning the argument.

The young professionals can adopt some of the following approaches:

- **Choose the moment wisely.** Not every disagreement needs to be raised immediately. A private follow-up discussion often yields better results than a public confrontation.

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- **Use respectful and open-ended language.** Rather than saying “I disagree,” try:
 - “I see it a bit differently. May I share my perspective?”
 - “Would it be possible to consider another angle?”
- **Suggest solutions, not just problems.** Pointing out flaws is easy. Offering thoughtful alternatives shows initiative and teamwork.
- **Understand the bigger picture.** Sometimes, a decision is made based on factors you may not be aware of. Trust in leadership doesn’t mean blind acceptance, it means

recognizing your role in the broader context.

In other words

- When to talk
- What to talk
- How to talk

To manage the tension between honesty and hierarchy, following are some of the practical strategies that professionals especially young CAs can adopt:

Understand the Culture

Each workplace has its own rules - some written, many unwritten. Observe how others communicate with senior leaders/ bosses. Are people encouraged to speak freely or is there a more formal structure in place? Understanding culture

helps you tailor your approach. What works in one company may not be appropriate in another.

Pick Your Battles

Not every issue needs to be debated. Focus your energy on matters that truly affect outcomes, ethics or risk. By choosing your battles wisely, you maintain credibility and avoid being labeled as unnecessarily difficult.

Build Your Reputation First

When you have built a track record of good judgment and loyalty, your views are more likely to be heard and respected even when they differ. Credibility gives your voice weight.

Respect Hierarchy, Even in Dissent

Even when you don’t agree with a decision, acknowledging the leader’s position and responsibilities is essential. This shows maturity and earns respect.

Stay Emotionally Intelligent

Tone, body language and timing matter just as much as the words you use. Staying calm, confident and professional during disagreement reflects emotional intelligence, a key trait of leadership.

Study of sufficient and relevant information, analysis and conclusion choosing the best possible options

Professionals who succeed in different environments are those who understand and adopt this skill. They know that honest disagreement does not need to be loud and quiet agreement does not always mean weakness. True strength lies in being able to think independently while acting collaboratively.

Agreeing with your boss doesn't mean giving up your voice. It means understanding how and when to express your voice in a

way that maintains respect and moves the organization forward.

As young Chartered Accountants grow in their careers from audit firms to corporations, from juniors to team leaders this ability to balance respect, judgment and communication becomes their greatest asset.

It's Not About Always Being Right It's About Being Wise:

The goal is not to win every debate or prove every point. The very beauty of healthy debate is you must agree to disagree. The goal is to contribute meaningfully, earn trust and support the success of your team and organization. Knowing

when to speak up and how to do it wisely is a mark of professional maturity. Ultimately a team works for value creation. As professional accountants, we are trained to apply judgment, challenge assumptions and act with integrity. But just as important is knowing how to communicate that judgment within the culture we work in.

Finally, professional success is not just about technical knowledge. It's about strategic awareness, emotional intelligence and the wisdom to navigate disagreement with grace.

Blue Economy

The Way to Sustainable Development of Bangladesh

Dr. Mohammad Omar Faruq¹ | Dr. Munira Sultana²

The Authors are:

¹Professor
Department of Accounting &
Information Systems
Jagannath University

²Professor
Department of Economics
Jagannath University

The article was reviewed by
Dr. Jamshed S A Choudhury FCA

Abstract

This article highlights the potential of a maritime economy to elevate Bangladesh to high-income status, fulfill Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and mitigate the risk of Dutch disease through the sustainable utilization of marine resources. Bangladesh is currently the second-largest garment exporter globally, following China. Ready-Made Garments (RMG) account for 80 percent of overall exports in Bangladesh. The economy would be susceptible to any abrupt external disruption. If apparel prices decline, total exports will decrease due to reliance only on the Garments Sector. The phenomenon is termed the "resource curse," which can potentially be alleviated by diversifying export items or sectors. A potential answer is the BLUE Economy. Geographically, Bangladesh is endowed by the Bay of Bengal, making the Blue Economy highly suitable for the country. This article examines the emerging prospects of the economic sector and the future of Bangladesh through the utilization of the Blue Economy.

Introduction

The Blue Economy refers to economic activities that are directly linked to the oceans and marine environments. Although the term "Blue Economy" is

commonly used, it does not yet have a universally accepted definition (Bollmann, 2010). The concept gained international prominence during the United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development (Rio+20), held in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil, in June 2012 (Smith-Godfrey, 2016). Several maritime industries are recognized as core components of the Blue Economy (Pauli, 2010). It encompasses a broad spectrum of marine-related operations and activities. According to Islam et al. (2018), twenty-six distinct marine economic functions—including fisheries, maritime trade and shipping, energy production, tourism, coastal protection, and maritime surveillance—are considered essential elements of the Blue Economy.

The primary objective of the Blue Economy is to ensure the sustainable and efficient use of marine resources across oceans, ports, and coastal areas while minimizing environmental harm and promoting human welfare. It emphasizes the development of innovative recycling systems and organic methods to transform human-generated waste into useful resources. This approach facilitates the productive use of marine assets at both national and international levels, thereby fostering economic development and enhancing social well-being.

Fundamentally, the Blue Economy represents an effort to decouple socio-economic progress from environmental degradation while maximizing the benefits derived from marine ecosystems. It promotes the concept of sustainable prosperity that safeguards the environment—particularly marine biodiversity—while improving the quality of life for all citizens. The notion of the Blue Economy, though relatively new in Bangladesh and South Asia, focuses on harnessing marine resources to achieve long-term economic sustainability.

This study aims to explore the potential of the Blue Economy in Bangladesh and assess its

contribution to national development. It highlights the alignment between the Blue Economy framework and the broader sustainable development agenda, underscoring its economic, social, and environmental dimensions as well as its potential to enhance GDP. The research also identifies key opportunities across different economic sectors for the advancement of the Blue Economy, along with the challenges that may hinder progress. Moreover, it encourages strategic thinking and policy action to effectively utilize marine resources, maximize benefits, and address obstacles through appropriate interventions.

This study concludes that Bangladesh possesses the capacity to successfully implement the Blue Economy model. However, this requires strong political commitment and institutional dedication—both of which have already begun to emerge in the country. Continued research, policy development, and widespread social awareness are essential to ensure the effective realization of the Blue Economy's potential in Bangladesh.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this paper are as follows:

- To assess the current status of the Blue Economy in Bangladesh.
- To establish a conceptual framework for the implementation of a Sustainable Blue Economy in Bangladesh.
- To ascertain the potential of the Blue Economy in Bangladesh.
- To identify the restrictions and obstacles facing Bangladesh in the successful implementation of the Blue Economy and to propose policy recommendations to solve these challenges.

Blue Economy

The Way to Sustainable Development of Bangladesh

Rationale of the Study

In today's era of globalization, no country can depend entirely on its land-based resources for economic growth. Therefore, the exploration and utilization of alternative sources of wealth have become essential—especially for developing nations like Bangladesh. The marine resources available within Bangladesh's maritime territory offer vast potential for diversification and economic expansion, thereby reducing the country's overreliance on terrestrial assets.

Bangladesh, with its extensive coastline along the Bay of Bengal—the largest bay in the world—holds immense opportunities for growth in various sectors. Industries such as maritime transportation (including shipbuilding and shipping), energy production (oil, gas, and renewable

sources), fisheries and aquaculture, marine information and communication technology (ICT), and coastal tourism can play pivotal roles in advancing the nation's economy.

To ensure the long-term sustainability of these initiatives, Bangladesh must pursue strategies that promote a Sustainable Blue Economy (SBE). This requires the formulation and implementation of well-coordinated government policies and strategic actions designed to harness marine resources responsibly while maximizing their economic benefits.

Literature Review

Numerous articles published in Bangladeshi national newspapers have discussed the emerging prospects of the Blue Economy. On May 14, 2018, The Daily Star featured an article by Harun Ur Rashid highlighting

Bangladesh's maritime victory and its potential economic benefits. The report noted that Bangladesh possesses a maritime area covering 200 nautical miles of exclusive economic zone and an additional 354 nautical miles of continental shelf resources. Experts estimate that the country's marine resources constitute about 81 percent of the total resources found within its land territory. The article also mentioned that the marine ecosystem hosts around 500 species of fish in addition to snails, shellfish, crabs, sharks, octopuses, and other aquatic species, suggesting that the nation could harness resources valued at approximately Tk. 12,000 crore (equivalent to 1.2 billion USD).

Similarly, on March 12, 2017, the Dhaka Tribune published an article emphasizing the opportunities for cruise and maritime tourism. It reported that visits by the U.S.-based international luxury cruise line Silversea had inaugurated a new era of sea tourism in Bangladesh. The arrival of these cruise tourists generated around Tk. 70 lakh for local businesses while also providing significant government revenue, according to industry sources.

An analytical article published in The Financial Express on February 6, 2018, examined the Blue Economy's potential impact on national growth.

Economists suggested that effective utilization of marine resources could enable Bangladesh's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) to reach an impressive 10 percent growth rate within the next decade. Additionally, a World Bank article titled "Bangladesh is Thinking Big by Thinking Blue" (April 1, 2018) underscored the vast opportunities and challenges inherent in managing such a large-scale ocean-based economy.

Beyond media coverage, several research studies and academic discussions have also explored the Blue Economy's potential. In July 2017, Md. Maruf Hossain of the Institute of Marine Science & Fisheries, University of Chittagong, published "The Prospects and Challenges on the Sustainable Development of Blue Economy in Bangladesh." His research focused on the country's sustainable development through marine resource utilization and analyzed new economic sectors associated with the Green Economy that could contribute to national growth. Another significant study, "The Prospects of Blue Economy to Promote Bangladesh into a Middle-Income Country" (May 22, 2018), by Md. Monjur Hasan of the Ocean University of China, explored sectoral contributions of the Blue Economy and identified potential challenges the government may encounter.

Sustainable development, as a guiding principle, aims to meet human development goals while ensuring the continued availability of natural resources and ecosystem services upon which economic and social systems depend. This concept envisions a society where living standards and resource use meet human needs without compromising ecological integrity. Although modern interpretations of sustainable development largely stem from the 1987 Brundtland Report, the idea has roots in earlier discussions of sustainable resource management and twentieth-century environmental movements. Over time, the focus has expanded to encompass economic growth, social equity, and environmental protection for future generations. "Sustainability" thus represents the long-term equilibrium between human activity and natural systems, while "sustainable development" describes the processes leading toward that equilibrium.

Integrating the ocean economy into the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) has become essential. This integration should extend beyond the earlier Millennium Development Goal 7B, which addressed fish stocks and marine conservation. The SDG framework, particularly Goal 14—"Conserve and sustainably use the oceans, seas, and

marine resources for sustainable development"—emphasizes this need. Other related goals include SDG 12 (responsible consumption and production), SDG 13 (climate action), and SDG 15 (life on land). Specific targets under SDG 14 include reducing marine pollution, protecting coastal ecosystems, mitigating ocean acidification, regulating fisheries, restoring fish stocks, enforcing international maritime laws, eliminating illegal and destructive fishing, and removing harmful fishing subsidies. Additional areas of focus include developing fair access and benefit-sharing mechanisms for marine bio-prospecting, promoting research and development in marine renewable energy (wind, wave, tidal, and biomass), and investing in sustainable coastal and maritime tourism.

The concept of the Blue Economy gained global prominence through Gunter Pauli's book "The Blue Economy: 10 Years, 100 Innovations, 100 Million Jobs." It advocates for a model that integrates ocean-based economic development with social inclusion, environmental protection, and innovative business practices. Oceans cover nearly two-thirds of the Earth's surface and are fundamental to sustaining life by providing food, minerals, and oxygen, absorbing greenhouse gases, regulating climate, and

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...serving as trade and transport routes. Today, over three billion people live near coastal areas, and this number is expected to grow.

The Blue Economy is often regarded as an evolution of the Green Economy framework that was endorsed during the 2012 United Nations Conference on Sustainable Development (Rio+20). Its primary goal is to enhance human welfare and social equity while minimizing environmental harm. The approach emphasizes the sustainable use and management of marine biodiversity, ecosystem services, and genetic resources, along with strengthening global efforts for climate change adaptation and mitigation. Worldwide, the ocean-based economy supports approximately 350 million jobs in sectors such as fishing, aquaculture, tourism, and marine research, while over one billion people depend on fish as their main source of protein.

As stated in the Blue Economy Concept Paper (2012), oceans cover about 72 percent of the Earth's surface and account for more than 95 percent of the biosphere. They play a critical role in producing oxygen, absorbing carbon dioxide, recycling nutrients, and regulating the planet's temperature. Marine and coastal ecosystems are vital sources of food, employment,

transportation, and international trade. They also underpin the global tourism industry, encompassing both conventional "sun, sand, and sea" attractions and the growing field of eco-tourism. Additionally, seabeds contribute around 32 percent of the world's hydrocarbon supply, and advancements in technology continue to unlock new opportunities for marine resource exploration—from bioprospecting to seabed mineral extraction. The oceans also possess vast potential for generating renewable "blue energy" through wind, wave, tidal, and biomass sources. Thus, the maritime domain remains central to enhancing trade connectivity and fostering global economic growth.

Opportunities for Blue Economy Expansion in Bangladesh

The South Asian region enjoys a distinctive geographical position along the Bay of Bengal—one of the world's most significant and resource-rich bays—bordered by Bangladesh in the north and India in the west. This strategic location holds immense potential for advancing the Blue Economy.

Key sectors of the Blue Economy are viewed as crucial for optimizing the utilization of ocean-based resources within Bangladesh's existing maritime jurisdiction. Effective

management of these resources — through comprehensive planning, public-private collaboration, and strategic investment—can establish a strong foundation for sustainable revenue generation and economic growth. Conversely, if marine resources and potential industries are managed under the guiding principles of biodiversity conservation, environmental stewardship, and scientific understanding, the Blue Economy could also become instrumental in addressing climate change challenges in coastal areas. Such an approach would foster employment creation and significantly enhance the livelihoods of people living in coastal zones, islands, and other peripheral regions of Bangladesh.

To achieve this vision, a collaborative and inclusive approach involving all relevant stakeholders is essential. It is important to identify and transform existing challenges into opportunities to ensure that Blue Economy development does not lead to unsustainable or ecologically harmful practices driven solely by short-term economic gains. In the context of Bangladesh, this requires the formulation of a comprehensive maritime spatial plan to coordinate activities among Blue Economy sectors and stakeholders, thereby ensuring

balanced and sustainable marine development.

Blue Economy of Bangladesh

The Oceanic Economy, commonly known as the Blue Economy, has emerged as a crucial development agenda aimed at ensuring the efficient and sustainable use of oceans, seas, and marine resources to achieve long-term development goals. Among the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), Goal 14 specifically focuses on the conservation and sustainable utilization of marine resources for sustainable development.

Marine ecosystems provide essential food and energy resources that are fundamental to human survival. Ignoring nearly three-fourths of the Earth's surface would make it impossible to achieve global sustainable economic growth by 2030. Recognizing this, Bangladesh has undertaken various initiatives to promote the sustainable management of its oceanic and marine resources, aligning its national policies with the objectives of SDG-14 to ensure inclusive and sustainable development.

Bangladesh has a coastline stretching approximately 710 kilometers, with an Exclusive Economic Zone (EEZ) extending 200 nautical miles into the Bay of Bengal. Marine

fisheries contribute about 19.40 percent of the country's total fish production, while around 81 percent of international tourists visit Cox's Bazar—the country's prime coastal destination. The maritime domain plays a pivotal role in Bangladesh's socio-economic growth by fostering trade, employment, and investment, particularly across the southern coastal regions.

Following the resolution of maritime boundary disputes, Bangladesh gained a newly defined economic zone in the Bay of Bengal, unlocking vast opportunities for marine resource utilization. In response, the Government of Bangladesh (GoB) has initiated several measures to develop the Blue Economy. Since 2015, multiple national-level discussions, workshops, and seminars have been organized to explore its potential. The country's Seventh Five-Year Plan (7FYP) outlines twelve strategic initiatives designed to foster a dynamic and sustainable Blue Economy, covering areas such as fisheries, renewable energy, human resource development, transshipment, tourism, and climate change adaptation.

In 2017, the Government established the "Blue Economy Cell" under the Ministry of Foreign Affairs (MoFA) to coordinate and oversee Blue Economy activities across different sectoral ministries. The

Blue Economy holds immense potential to strengthen Bangladesh's national economy. The Ministry of Foreign Affairs has identified twenty-six prospective sectors within this framework, including fisheries, maritime trade and shipping, energy, coastal protection, tourism, and maritime security and surveillance, all of which can collectively drive sustainable economic transformation in Bangladesh.

Shipping

In 2018, approximately 90 percent of Bangladesh's international freight trade was carried out through maritime routes, underscoring the sector's dominant role in the nation's external commerce. This indicates that the country's economic growth is likely to remain heavily dependent on maritime freight trade in the future. To retain a significant portion of freight revenue within the domestic economy, it is essential to provide incentives for local shipping companies to expand their fleets by adding new vessels. Additionally, greater attention should be directed toward enhancing coastal shipping, seaport operations, passenger ferry services, inland waterway transport, and the shipbuilding and ship recycling industries to promote sustainable and inclusive economic development.

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Fishery

Experts estimate that the Bay of Bengal hosts around 500 fish species, along with a wide variety of marine organisms such as snails, shellfish, crabs, sharks, and octopuses. Bangladesh is projected to harvest approximately 0.70 million tons of fish annually from the Bay's total stock of about 8 million tons. Globally, nearly 15 percent of dietary protein originates from marine sources, underscoring the critical importance of conserving these resources for the millions who depend on them for food and livelihood. The true potential of Bangladesh's offshore gas reserves remains largely unexplored; however, given the country's existing onshore gas fields and its geological similarities with neighboring Myanmar, it is plausible that substantial offshore gas deposits exist within Bangladesh's maritime boundaries. Beyond oil and gas, other ocean-based resources—such as sea salt, renewable marine energy, blue energy (osmosis), biomass, sand and gravel extraction, and marine genetic materials—deserve greater attention. Harnessing this vast potential could play a pivotal role in advancing Bangladesh's sustainable economic development in the years ahead.

Tourism

Coastal tourism represents the largest segment of the global tourism market, contributing approximately 5 percent to the world's Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and generating between 6 to 7 percent of total global employment. It ranks among the top five sources of export earnings for 150 countries and serves as the principal source of foreign exchange for nearly half of the Least Developed Countries (LDCs). The sector includes various activities such as (a) beach-based recreation and tourism, (b) seaside tourist engagements, and (c) maritime activities like yachting and marina operations. When managed sustainably, coastal tourism can create substantial employment opportunities and help reduce poverty. For Bangladesh, the tourism industry holds significant potential to earn foreign currency, boost GDP growth, and contribute to achieving the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) by 2030. The nation's 75 offshore islands offer valuable opportunities for the expansion of both domestic and international tourism.

Future of Exploration

By utilizing suitable technology to explore and harness these marine resources, Bangladesh's economy can experience significant growth. Bangladesh

established a delineated maritime zone in the Bay of Bengal following a protracted resolution of its maritime border disputes with India and Myanmar. Bangladesh should focus on enhancing its Blue Economy to effectively harness its extensive maritime territory and resources while maintaining a sustainable equilibrium between the conservation of the marine ecosystem and the utilization of marine resources. Bangladesh can generate more opportunities for economic growth by attracting new investments in marine trade and commerce.

Fish Export from Bangladesh

Tables 1 and 2 indicate that export revenues from fish and prawns are rising, with Bangladesh averaging 252.95 crores from 1972 to 1992. Data are sourced from the time series database of Bangladeshi banks. During the period from 1993 to 2024, the average receipts amount to 2,615 crores of taka. Tables 3 and 4 clearly demonstrate that fish export receipts exhibit an increased trend, indicating that Bangladesh is increasingly generating revenue from exports. However, throughout 2008-2009, it had a significant decrease followed by a subsequent rebound. The deviation from the trend may be attributed to political turmoil and the floods of 1998.

Table 1: Summary statistics for export receipts from fish pawns from 1972 to 1992

	Fish Export Tk. Cores
Mean	252.9524
Median	182.0000
Maximum	794.0000
Minimum	2.000000
Std. Dev	251.8951
Sum	5312.000
Sun sq dev	1269023
Observations	21

Source: Bangladesh Bank

Table-2 Summary statistics for export receipts from fish pawn during 1993 -2024

	Fish Export Tk. Cores
Mean	2615.500
Median	2430.000
Maximum	4758.000
Minimum	1013.000
Observation	22

Source: Bangladesh Bank

Table-3 shows that in Bangladesh fisheries production from 1992 -2024

Items	Fisheries GDP
Mean	1458879
Median	1002567
Maximum	3548115
Minimum	640070.0
Std. Dev	905711.4
Observation	43

Financial evaluation of major blue economics sectors in Bangladesh**Table-4 Financial evaluation of major blue economics sectors in Bangladesh (Million US\$)**

Economic Sector	Marine fisheries	Oil	Sea salt	Sand, Mineral and Coals	Water Transport	Trade & Shipping
2019	843.75	21.9	119.25	735.18	1,215.14	31,390.15
2020	949.48	23.84	123.48	944.39	1330.36	36,178.04
2021	1107.42	26.82	160.9	1183.79	1450.21	41,728.94
2022	1231.06	28.77	206	1452.46	1606.1	47,156.44
2023	1384.77	29.35	212.35	1644.08	1682.31	52,078.80
2024	1475.66	34.05	214.84	1893.14	1,816.67	58,466.90

Sources: Data adopted from Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics (BBS, 2024)

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Conclusion

The Bay of Bengal and its coastal areas provide a significant resource base and have established a new economic frontier for Bangladesh. Numerous industries within the blue economy have opportunities for advancement to attain food security and economic development goals. It may be argued that Bangladesh must enhance awareness regarding the utilization of maritime resources to effectuate socio-economic improvements in the lives of its citizens. The blue economy may serve as an optimal alternative for Bangladesh to attain sustainable economic growth. This study aims to elucidate the current state of Bangladesh's blue economy. The data indicates that marine output and aquaculture are on the rise, which is a positive development. However, our blue industry is adversely affected by recurrent floods. We lack adequately trained, skilled, and educated people resources across several marine industries. The government must establish a future policy framework to ensure the success of the Blue Economy. This framework may emphasize structural collaboration, the translation of research into products, a comprehensive approach to the Blue Economy, and the motivation and training of younger generations.

Recommendations

Informed by a comprehensive examination of policy formulation, Bangladesh should implement several critical measures in this area. Policymakers should implement the following policies essential for our comprehensive socio-economic growth. In the preliminary phase, a 3-5 year strategy for the Blue Economy Project will be developed through the collaboration of the Ministry of Fisheries and Livestock, Ministry of Finance, Ministry of Shipping, Ministry of Water Resources, Ministry of Planning, and Ministry of ICT for technological assistance. A panel of experts from many disciplines, including Marine Biologists, Fisheries and Aquaculture professionals, Marine Trade experts, and Economists (Nature and Resources economists, Macroeconomists), might be established to monitor and evaluate the SBE initiative. No policy or action should be undertaken without the endorsement of the expert panel.

- Bangladesh might seek guidance or recommendations from one of the countries recognized by UNEP (2015) as a success story in the Blue Economy for technical and other support. We can engage in a technological knowledge

exchange and collaborate with professionals.

- To achieve a Sustainable Blue Economy, it is imperative to implement measures that mitigate marine and ocean water pollution, as well as other forms of environmental deterioration.
- Government, corporations, and community partnerships (public-private partnerships) should be cultivated through business connections and integrated infrastructure.
- We must implement waste disposal methods include recycling, incineration, gasification, bioreactor landfills, composting, and anaerobic digestion.
- Furthermore, we must establish an Integrated Waste Management (IWM) system for this specific objective.

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The Role of Green Finance in the Sustainable Economic Growth of Bangladesh

Habiba Akhter ACA

The Author is an Associate Member, ICAB and AGM (Finance & Accounts) United Group

Abstract

Green finance has been an important tool of sustainable development in Bangladesh to fight climate change and spur economic growth. Green bonds, investments in alternative energy, and other environmentally friendly projects are the primary areas of interest of this study, which analyzes the role of green finance in the economic development of Bangladesh. Its secondary data sources demonstrate how green finance (raising funds to support environmental projects and incentivizing companies to engage in sustainable operations) could enable Bangladesh to attain sustainable growth in the long

term. Indicatively, over BDT 3,500 crore has been invested in the renewable energy sector in Bangladesh in 2024 alone. It also determines the barriers to successful implementation of green finance such as regulatory frameworks, infrastructure problems, and lack of awareness. To make sure that green finance makes a huge contribution to the future of the Bangladesh economy. Recommendations on the way to overcome these challenges are outlined at the end of the paper. The paper will contribute to the ongoing dialogues on green finance inclusion of green projects into the mainstream economic policy of Bangladesh by offering practical policies to enhance the number of investments in green projects.

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By bridging these gaps, green finance can serve as a catalyst for long-term sustainable development and economic resilience within the country.

Key Words: Green Finance, Sustainable Growth, Climate Change, Bangladesh Economy, Green Bonds, Renewable Energy, Environmental Projects.

Introduction

Green finance, it describes capital investment and financial instruments that incorporate economic activities in environmental sustainability and low-carbon transition. This covers the investments in programs that focus on energy efficiency, environmental safety, and renewable energy. Green finance has become an important aspect of the development agenda in Bangladesh as the country manages the twin challenges of

economic growth and climate change. To illustrate this, Bangladesh is planning to install BDT 6,000 crore worth of renewable energy-generating plants in the next five years with the aim of generating 10 per cent of its energy needs by this year. Investments that are resilient and sustainable are increasingly becoming important especially as Bangladesh grapple with the impacts of cyclones and floods. All these natural calamities cost the economy approximately BDT 3,000 crore in a year. Green finance has garnered much interest in recent years due to the role it plays in ensuring sustainable economic development in our country due to its ability to support climate-resilient infrastructure, promoting investment in green technologies, and enhancing environmental protection. The realization of the potential

economic benefits of a greener economy, such as creating jobs, managing resources more efficiently and sustainable development over the long term, is evident in the attempts of the government to integrate green finance into the mainstream financial system. Green finance therefore has a bright future as one of the most important elements in overall growth strategy of Bangladesh.

Literature Review

Green finance is increasingly recognized as an important tool for dealing with environmental issues and promoting green economic growth at the same time. The role it plays in developed or developing countries has been the focus of many studies, and much attention has been placed on how it contributes to the transition to a low-carbon climate-resilient economy (Hussain et al., 2021). In order to tackle the mounting environmental issues, several scholars have highlighted the need of greater institutionalized green finance projects within the framework of Bangladesh (Rahman and Ahmed, 2019). Green finance can become the most important part of the financial system, and in 2023 Bangladesh issued the first green bond, in the amount of BDT 200 crore. Examples of green finance products that are believed to play a vital role in enhancing the commitment of Bangladesh to climate

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adaptation and mitigation include climate risk insurance, environmental impact funds, and green bonds (Rahman, 2020). These tools aid climate resistant infrastructure, sustainable development projects and mobilisation of both government and private sector investments towards environmental projects. In many studies, the need to increase the awareness of consumers and financial institutions and the need to have an effective regulatory framework to facilitate green finance in Bangladesh have been pointed out. Advancing green finance mechanisms in Bangladesh will definitely emerge as a core factor in long-term national development.

Objectives

The research objectives are as follows:

1. To assess the role played by green finance in the sustainable economic development of Bangladesh.
2. To identify the hurdles that Bangladesh has to overcome in the process of developing green finance.
3. To examine potential benefits and opportunities of green finance to the economy of Bangladesh. In order to give recommendations on how to improve the implementation and

effectiveness of green finance in Bangladesh.

4. To provide a comprehensive picture of how green finance can facilitate sustainable economic development in Bangladesh, these objectives aim to draw attention to the key opportunities and challenges to its adoption.

Methods of Research

The study is qualitative in nature, where secondary data obtained via government reports, international organizations, articles in the academic literature, and case studies are used. Content analysis was applied to analyze the data in order to have an idea about the prevailing condition of green finance in Bangladesh and how it is playing its role in the sustainable economic development of Bangladesh. By adopting such an approach, the issues and possibilities associated with the integration of green finance into the economy of the country could be analyzed.

Contribution to Economic Development

Green finance can contribute significantly to the economic growth of Bangladesh by encouraging investments in environmentally friendly projects, improving energy efficiency, and reducing the

adverse impact of climate change. Green finance plays a significant role in supporting sustainable development in Bangladesh through the following aspects:

Building More Renewable Energy. Solar, wind and biomass are some of the renewable energy sources which are highly abundant in Bangladesh. Solar power investments have hit BDT 1,200 crore in 2024 with a target to expand solar power capacity by 300 MW annually. Green finance can help accelerate investments in these sectors, both by reducing the carbon footprint of the country and by increasing employment and energy security. Green finance projects help the government achieve its goal of generating 10 percent of the national

electricity using renewable energy sources by this year. The development of solar energy initiatives has the potential to empower local communities and create economic opportunities over time, especially in rural regions.

Infrastructure. Green finance can be particularly significant when it comes to financing climate-resilient infrastructure including flood barriers, water management systems as well as sustainable agriculture projects. Climate threat is especially present in Bangladesh, and with green finance funding the response to reduce disaster risks and adapt to climate challenge, it will reduce the impact of climate-driven disasters. Within green finance, an amount of BDT 500 crore

was reserved to be used on climate adaptation projects in two years back.

Economic Diversification and Creation of Jobs. Investment in green technologies and renewable energy sources, especially in areas of waste management, clean energy and protection of the environment has potential to create new employment opportunities. It is hoped that by 2026 the green energy sector will create 200,000 new jobs on its own.

Promoting Green Consciousness. Green finance motivates the finance sector to invest in energy efficiency technologies, waste management strategies, and sustainable manufacturing processes by offering incentives to companies to adopt environmentally friendly practices. This encourages environmental stewardship over time and the creation of a circular economy by minimizing waste and reusing resources.

Green Financing in Bangladesh has been transforming continuously as a result of the Bangladesh Bank directives. Till the end of 2024 and early 2025, banks and financial institutions must allocate at least 5% of total term loans for green financing. The table below highlights the sectoral composition and performance trend for the past 5 years based on the Bangladesh Bank Quarterly Reviews:

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Major Sector	Key Sub Sectors	Estimated Share (%)
Energy Efficiency	Energy-saving machinery, Green RMG (Garment) factories	-35-40%
Renewable Energy	Solar home systems, Solar irrigation, Wind & Biogas	-15-20%
Waste Management	Effluent Treatment Plants (ETP), Solid waste recycling	15%
Green Agriculture	Organic farming, Bio-fertilizer, Precision irrigation	12%
ECO Friendly Bricks	Tunnel kilns, Hybrid Hoffman Kilns (HHK)	10%
Others	Green Buildings (LEED), Water conservation	5%

(Source: Bangladesh Bank)

Trend of Performances by Year (5 Yearly Disbursement): While 'Sustainable Finance', which includes social and CMSME lending, has reached almost 40% of the total credit in 2025, the specific Green Finance portion was really volatile due to global economic conditions:

Year	Green Finance Disbursement (Approx. BDT Billion)	Key Trend
2021	72.30	Initial recovery post-COVID; focus on Green RMG.
2022	88.50	Rapid growth due to the Green Transformation Fund.
2023	121.40	Peak investment year; high adoption of LEED factory standards.
2024	275.60	Significant jump in quarterly reporting and policy compliance.
2025 (Est.)	315.0+	Shift toward mandatory 5% targets for all scheduled banks.

(Source: Bangladesh Bank)

Obstacles to Green Finance in Bangladesh

Although the benefits of using green finance can be substantial, there are several barriers that inhibit its use on a large scale in Bangladesh:

Lack of Knowledge and awareness. One of the primary obstacles to the successful implementation of green finance products and services is the lack of knowledge and understanding on how to use green finance products and services. Both consumers and financial institutions often do not have the information that

they need to make prudent decisions regarding green investments. It is this lack of information that could hinder the growth of the green finance industry and deny it the potential it has.

Inadequate Regulation. The green financial regulation system of Bangladesh remains at its initial stages despite the establishment of environmental sustainability promotion policies.

Stronger legal frameworks are required to ensure transparency, encourage green investments, and assure investors. In the

absence of clear and enforceable regulations, the financial institutions will not be willing to fund green projects, which will reduce the overall contribution of the green finance initiatives in the country.

Large First Investment Cost. Green technologies often require more at the initial stages when compared with traditional options. Finding capital to finance a large scale green project is not easy in a country such as Bangladesh where capital access is limited.

There is limited access to Green Financial Products. Many

financial institutions in Bangladesh do not yet provide specialized green financial products such as green bonds or climate bonds because they lack experience in environmental finance and perceive these products as risky. To encourage green financial investment, it is crucial to increase the variety of green financial products offered to the public and businesses.

Conclusion

Green finance can provide Bangladesh with an excellent opportunity to fight climate change and support sustainable economic development. A variety of challenges should be met on its way to successful implementation, though, including lack of knowledge, legal constraints, and financial constraints. Green finance can help Bangladesh achieve economic resilience and environmental sustainability through improving the regulatory framework, increasing financial literacy, and developing green financial products. The government, financial institutions and the private sector have to work together to ensure that green finance will be one of the key

drivers to growth and development of Bangladesh in the future. Green finance adoption in Bangladesh can readily resolve related urgent environmental challenges and enhance the long-term economic development. To realise this potential, it is important to overcome the challenges which hinder the development of the sector. Increasing the access to green finance products, improving the regulatory environment, and raising awareness are the three actions that can help Bangladesh to lead the sustainable economic future. Green finance will remain a vital component of Bangladesh's development, as building a more sustainable and resilient economy requires collaboration among multiple stakeholders.

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Advancing Gender Diversity in Internal Audit

A Global and Regional Review of Women’s Participation

Nanda Dulal Saha FCA

The Author is a
Fellow Member, ICAB
and
Director, Internal Audit
BRAC

Abstract

This article analyses global and regional trends concerning women’s participation in the internal audit profession, emphasising the ongoing gender disparities. It highlights the “leaky pipeline” phenomenon, which refers to the diminishing representation of women in higher leadership roles, primarily due to structural barriers such as organisational bias, inflexible work arrangements, and travel safety concerns. Currently, women constitute approximately one-third of the global internal audit workforce but remain underrepresented in senior and executive positions. In North America, Australia, and certain parts of Europe, there has been an increase in women’s representation in audit leadership roles; however, regions like South Asia continue to lag due to deeply rooted societal constraints.

A significant aspect of the article is a multi-phase case study of BRAC, the world’s largest development organisation. This case exemplifies how sustained and targeted interventions can effectively address these challenges. BRAC’s Internal Audit Department implemented a comprehensive, multi-phased strategy from 2007 to 2025, which included strong leadership commitment,

gender-inclusive policies—such as flexible scheduling, enhanced travel safety measures, and gender-sensitivity training—formal mentoring, and a supportive organisational culture. These initiatives led to notable improvements in the recruitment, retention, and advancement of women within the department. This approach aligns with international best practices in gender mainstreaming, making BRAC a benchmark for organisations worldwide.

The findings underscore that fostering gender diversity in the audit profession necessitates integrated and long-term strategies. The article distils these insights into actionable recommendations, advocating for the execution of internal gender audits; the adoption of supportive policies, including flexible work arrangements and robust safety protocols; the establishment of formal mentoring & bias-awareness programmes; and the enforcement of accountability through diversity metrics linked to leadership evaluations. Implementing such measures can enable organisations to cultivate a more equitable and effective audit function, ultimately enhancing governance outcomes.

Introduction

The internal audit profession stands at a pivotal moment,

The article was reviewed by
Zareen Mahmud Hosen FCA

experiencing a transformative shift in its gender dynamics. This evolution marks the beginning of a new era, where gender diversity is increasingly acknowledged as vital for the profession's effectiveness and its contribution to robust corporate governance. The benefits of such diversity are well-documented; research from respected organisations such as the Institute of Internal Auditors (IIA) and global major audit firms consistently shows that audit teams with diverse gender representation achieve better governance outcomes, offer deeper insights into organisational risks, and encourage more ethically sound decision-making.

Despite the evident advantages and the rising number of women entering the field, a significant challenge persists: the "leaky pipeline"^③. This term describes the phenomenon where women, although they constitute a

considerable segment of entry-level internal audit professionals, encounter barriers that hinder their progression into mid-level and executive leadership roles. This issue goes beyond individual career choices; it highlights deeper structural challenges within the profession and organisational frameworks that impede career advancement. The slower promotion rates and higher attrition for women compared to their male counterparts indicate that systemic obstacles, rather than just personal decisions, greatly limit women's leadership. Addressing these systemic barriers is crucial for the continued growth of the profession. This article will examine the global and regional contexts of women's participation, followed by a comprehensive case study demonstrating how strategic interventions can effectively address these challenges.

The Global Landscape of Gender Diversity in Internal Audit

Globally, the representation of women in internal audit is showing signs of improvement, though this progress is far from uniform across all regions and seniority levels. As of 2022, women comprised approximately 37% of the global internal audit workforce (IIA). Despite this encouraging overall representation, a significant disparity remains in executive positions, where women continue to be underrepresented, particularly in critical roles such as Chief Audit Executive (CAE)^①.

The landscape of gender representation displays significant regional variations. In Australia, the percentage of women in internal auditing reached 57% in 2021^④. Meanwhile, North America has shown remarkable advancement, with the proportion of women Chief Audit Executives (CAEs) rising from 33% in 2017 to an expected 47% by 2025^②. This upward trend highlights a positive movement toward gender equality in leadership roles within that area. Similarly, certain parts of Europe are approaching gender balance in specific leadership segments. However, regions such as the Middle East, Africa, and South Asia continue to fall behind, grappling with more deeply rooted challenges.

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South Asia: Deep-Rooted Barriers to Women's Advancement

In South Asia, women's participation in internal auditing remains significantly limited. Data from the IIA's Common Body of Knowledge (CBOK) indicates that only 7% of Chief Audit Executives (CAEs) in the region are women (2015)^⑥. Several factors contribute to this imbalance, including deeply rooted gender norms, safety concerns related to travel, and a lack of mentorship opportunities for aspiring women professionals. Furthermore, the overall workforce participation among working-age women in the region is less than one-third, leaving over 400 million women

A promising indicator for future progress lies in generational shifts. Among Millennial CAEs in North America, near gender parity has already been achieved^②. This development suggests that cultural and systemic changes, possibly influenced by evolving workplace expectations and sustained diversity initiatives over time, are beginning to yield results at younger leadership levels. This offers a forward-looking perspective, implying that if similar long-term, committed strategies are adopted in other regions, they too could witness accelerated cultural change and improved representation among future cohorts of leaders.

The benefits of such diversity are clear: organisations with diverse and inclusive audit teams demonstrate stronger risk governance and ethical decision-making, as outlined in the joint Deloitte-IIA report on DEI in internal audit^④.

Furthermore, PwC emphasises that gender diversity as a critical dimension of inclusion strengthens innovation, talent retention, and market responsiveness, enabling organisations to better reflect stakeholders and unlock competitive advantage^⑤.

Figure 1: A world map infographic highlighting regional women's participation in internal audit

Bangladesh in Focus: Societal Constraints and Emerging Opportunities

Bangladesh, a key country within South Asia, largely mirrors the broader regional trends concerning women's participation in professional and leadership roles. The statistics underscore a significant misalignment between women's talent potential and their actual representation in senior positions. As of July 2024, only 8.1%¹⁰ of the members of the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Bangladesh (ICAB) were women, a modest increase from 4.67% in 2014¹⁰. While this represents an improvement, a closer examination reveals that a 3.43% increase over a decade

excluded from formal employment⁷. The workforce participation rate for women in South Asia stands at 25.6%, while for men, it is 74.7%. According to the World Economic Forum's Global Gender Gap Report 2023, it will take an additional 149 years to close these gender gaps in the region¹³.

education and training, and demand-side constraints, including inflexible job structures, risks associated with fieldwork, and inherent gender bias. As a result, there is a narrow and fragile pipeline for women aspiring to enter the auditing profession.

The leadership gap is particularly striking in the financial sector. The International Finance Corporation (IFC, 2024) reveals that women occupy only 18% of senior leadership roles in South Asian banking institutions, which include countries like Bangladesh, Nepal, and Sri Lanka⁸. Representation among Chartered Accountants is also low, with only 9% in Pakistan, 22% in India, and around 30% in Sri Lanka⁹. This underrepresentation underscores both supply-side challenges, such as limited access to

Figure 2: An infographic illustrating the "leaky pipeline" in internal audit.

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Women's Representation in Audit & Finance in Bangladesh (2024)

(2014-2024) translates to less than 0.34% per year. In a related context, the Institute of Internal Auditors Bangladesh (IIAB) had a women membership of 8.94% in 2021, which only marginally grew to 9.25% by 2024. At this rate, achieving significant gender parity would require centuries, highlighting that such incremental changes are insufficient to address the scale of the gender gap. This situation underscores the critical need for stronger, systemic interventions to accelerate progress.

Within the banking sector, Bangladesh Bank reported that women constituted 17.6% of total employees by the end of 2024, yet their representation in senior management roles was significantly lower, at only 9.73%^⑪. These figures reflect broader societal limitations; the World Bank estimated in 2022 that women occupied only 8.9% of all senior and middle

management roles across various industries in Bangladesh^⑫. This persistent disparity between talent availability and leadership outcomes necessitates urgent institutional reform, sustained advocacy, and the implementation of measurable policies specifically designed to close the gender gap.

Case Study: BRAC's Blueprint for Gender Transformation in Internal Audit

BRAC, a prominent international development organisation founded in Bangladesh, demonstrates the efficacy of organisational commitment in advancing gender equality. Its dedication is deeply embedded in its policies and practices, which are designed to foster a workplace where women and other marginalised genders are empowered with equal

opportunities. This commitment is formalised through initiatives like the "Gender Justice and Diversity (GJ&D)" programme and the "BRAC Gender Policy Towards Gender Equity," both aimed at creating environments where women employees can develop and achieve their highest potential. Sir Fazle Hasan Abed, the founder of BRAC, said that "We have come far, but we still have a lot to accomplish in the field of women's empowerment. Once women realise their true potential, only then they will be able to write their own stories of success."^⑮

Setting the Stage: The Commitment of BRAC Internal Audit and Initial Challenges

The professional landscape for women in demanding fields, such as auditing in South Asia, particularly in Bangladesh, presents significant challenges. Factors such as frequent travel requirements, night stays at field locations leaving family behind, lack of women-friendly structures, cultural constraints, and a lack of gender sensitivity hinder women's entry and retention in this sector. In contrast, BRAC's Internal Audit Department stands out as a noteworthy success story. With a robust team of approximately 265 members, BRAC has achieved an impressive 22% women participation rate within

its Internal Audit function. This accomplishment reflects the organisation's strong institutional commitment and the strategic implementation of policies designed to cultivate a supportive and inclusive work environment.

Strategic Journey: A Four-Phase Empowerment Blueprint (2007-2025)

The transformation was not the result of a single intervention but rather a deliberate, multi-year strategy underpinned by consistent action and unwavering institutional commitment. This vision was executed through four distinct phases:

Phase 1: Laying the Foundation for Inclusivity (2007-2012):

The initial phase marked the beginning of our commitment to gender inclusivity, establishing a solid foundation through dedicated

gender-focused meetings. Senior management significantly reinforced this commitment by actively overseeing all gender-related issues. Our initiatives expanded to include raising awareness among all staff through comprehensive discussions and targeted training programmes. We also prioritised the involvement of Gender Focal Persons (GFPs) in various initiatives, specifically aimed at improving the representation of women within the workforce. Additionally, to enhance awareness, we initiated the celebration of International Women's Day. Progress in these areas was systematically monitored through quarterly reports submitted to the Executive Director (CEO), Managing Director, Senior Management, and the Board Audit Committee.

Phase 2: Enhancing the Workplace Experience (2013-2017): Building on our

foundational commitment, Phase 2 focused on implementing essential initiatives aimed at greatly improving the experience of women staff while directly tackling specific operational barriers. A key goal was to reduce obstacles during overnight field visits, which often deter women from the profession. Supervisors actively coordinated with relevant departments to prioritise allocating the nearest audit locations to women staff within their divisions. This practical shift, transitioning from general awareness to tangible operational changes, demonstrated a responsive strategy that effectively addressed real-world challenges. At the same time, a more respectful workplace was fostered by instituting a strict ban on any inappropriate "side talk" directed at women staff in the office. Women's involvement in departmental audits was increased to lessen the frequency of their required field visits, with a strategic assignment of at least two women staff members to each Internal Audit Department (IAD) Divisional Office. For officials at the Head Office, assignments were made to the nearest field locations within Dhaka. Alongside these operational adjustments, the department, with the backing of Human Resource Development (HRD) management, began recruiting

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Phase 4: Fostering Leadership and Well-being (2023-2025):

Building on the progress of previous phases, Phase 4 prioritised enhancing women's professional development and leadership representation, with a strong emphasis on their overall well-being. Targeted leadership training programmes for women were introduced, specifically designed to promote gender balance at mid and top management levels. Concurrently, the department actively cultivated a respectful and inclusive culture by addressing workplace microaggressions while strictly prohibiting disrespectful communication. This evolution in addressing subtle cultural nuances reflects a mature understanding of inclusion, recognising that true equity necessitates not only access but also a supportive and psychologically safe environment. The diversity of backgrounds and perspectives was actively championed. To further support well-being and flexibility, a policy permitting desk work during menstrual periods was implemented, alongside the introduction of a weekly work-from-anywhere initiative. These policies demonstrate a sophisticated understanding of the intrinsic link between well-being, productivity, and employee retention, marking a shift from merely "bringing women in" to

women into managerial roles through flexible policies. Throughout all these initiatives, prioritising the safety and security of women staff during field visits remained paramount.

Phase 3: Cultivating Comprehensive Support and Inclusion (2018-2022): This phase saw the adoption of a comprehensive strategy to enhance support for women in field operations and cultivate a more inclusive workplace. Key initiatives included prioritising women's needs in audit schedule allocations, ensuring they received the most favourable options and locations. To significantly enhance safety and comfort during travel and ensure women travelling alone can occupy two

seats on public transportation. We actively increased women's staff involvement in system audits as well as significant and high-risk audits, leveraging their expertise. Concurrently, gender sensitivity training was mandated for all supervisory personnel, and a pilot programme was launched to recruit women exclusively for Internal Audit Divisional offices, aiming to boost representation. Fostering collaboration, we instituted regular sharing sessions (Mon Khule Kotha bola/Speaking with an open heart) with senior management from the Human Resources Division (HRD) and Gender Justice & Diversity (GJ&D) to encourage open dialogue and effectively address challenges.

Measurable Impact: A Model of Success and Sustainable Change

BRAC’s sustained, multi-phased efforts have yielded remarkable and measurable results, transforming the landscape of its Internal Audit Department. Based on the progress, women’s participation has increased as follows:

actively fostering an environment where they can thrive within the organisation.

2026-2030 Initiatives to Enhance Women's Participation

Additional planned initiatives include: launching a Women in Audit Leadership Programme;

establishing partnerships with universities to build a women’s talent pipeline; creating gender-balanced recruitment panels; introducing a ‘Return to Audit’ scheme for women re-entering the workforce after career breaks; and offering internships for women students. We are also working on day care facilities for our staff, which will

assist in preventing sign-out from the profession after having child. Our objective is to elevate women’s representation within the Internal Audit Department to 30% by 2030. To reach this goal, we will implement a series of initiatives beginning in 2026. This phased approach will build on the successes of prior years and will emphasise recruitment,

Summary of BRAC Gender Initiatives (2007-2030)

Period	Key Initiatives
2007-2012	Foundation phase: gender meetings, awareness, GFPs, women’s day celebrations, reporting to Board.
2013-2017	Operational improvements: safe field visits, recruitment of women managers, strict anti-harassment policy.
2018-2022	Support & inclusion: priority in audit schedules, 2-seat travel policy, gender training, pilot recruitment for divisional offices.
2023-2025	Leadership & wellbeing: targeted leadership training, work-from-anywhere, menstrual flexibility policy, microaggressions policy.
2026-2030	Future roadmap: women in leadership, university partnerships, gender-balanced recruitment panels, return-to-audit scheme, scholarships & internships.

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retention, and leadership development.

Strategic Insights and Actionable Recommendations for Advancing Diversity

The transformative journey of BRAC's Internal Audit Department offers invaluable lessons for organisations globally, particularly those operating in challenging environments similar to South Asia. The success achieved underscores several critical factors that contribute to meaningful and lasting gender diversity.

Firstly, unwavering leadership commitment and accountability are paramount. Our decision to treat gender diversity as a strategic business objective, with senior management oversight and quarterly reporting to the highest levels, was fundamental. This top-down commitment ensures

that diversity initiatives are not merely peripheral HR functions but are embedded into the core governance and strategic concerns of the organisation, securing necessary resources and sustained focus.

Secondly, a phased, iterative approach is more effective than a "silver bullet" solution. Our multi-year strategy, evolving through distinct phases from foundational commitment to nuanced well-being policies, demonstrates that cultural and systemic change requires time and continuous effort. This gradual, deliberate implementation allows for adaptation and refinement, building trust and demonstrating tangible support over time.

Thirdly, addressing specific, practical barriers is crucial. Our focus on minimising field travel obstacles, ensuring safety during transit, and offering flexible work arrangements

directly confronted the unique challenges faced by women in the audit profession in Bangladesh. This pragmatic understanding of real-world impediments, coupled with tailored solutions, is far more impactful than generic diversity approaches.

Fourthly, a holistic approach to support that extends beyond recruitment to include retention, professional development, and overall well-being is essential. The increase in retention rates directly linked to safety and work redesign reforms clearly illustrates that investing in the lived experience of women in the workplace yields significant returns in talent longevity. This implies that for organisations to retain women, they must actively address the specific, practical concerns that often lead to attrition.

Finally, cultivating a truly inclusive culture that actively combats subtle biases and fosters open dialogue is vital. Our initiatives to address microaggressions and establish open communication channels ("Mon Khule Kotha bola/Speaking with an open heart") signify a mature understanding that true inclusion requires a supportive and psychologically safe daily environment. This continuous listening and adaptation allow organisations to identify and address evolving issues, fostering a sense of

psychological safety and ownership among employees.

Based on these insights, the following actionable recommendations are proposed for other organisations striving to enhance gender diversity in internal audit:

- Conduct Comprehensive Gender Audits: Systematically identify specific internal and external barriers to women's recruitment, retention, and advancement within the organisation and its operating environment.
- Implement Flexible Work Arrangements and Robust Safety Protocols: Tailor policies to address the unique challenges of the audit profession, such as frequent travel, by offering flexible hours, remote work options, and enhanced

safety measures for fieldwork.

- Develop Targeted Mentorship and Sponsorship Programmes: Create structured programmes that connect aspiring women professionals with senior leaders who can provide guidance, advocacy, and opportunities for career progression.
- Mandate Gender Sensitivity Training: Implement comprehensive and recurring training for all personnel, particularly supervisory and leadership levels, to raise awareness of unconscious biases and foster an inclusive workplace culture.
- Establish Clear Metrics and Accountability: Set measurable diversity goals

and link their achievement to senior leadership performance evaluations, ensuring that diversity is treated as a strategic imperative with tangible consequences.

- Foster an Inclusive Culture: Actively champion diverse perspectives, implement clear policies against all forms of discrimination and microaggressions, and create safe spaces for open dialogue and feedback from all employees.
- Collaborate with Industry Bodies and Educational Institutions: Work proactively with professional associations and universities to strengthen the women talent pipeline from the entry level, ensuring that women are encouraged and prepared for careers in internal audit.

A Call to Action: Addressing the Internal Audit Data Gap in the Subcontinent

A significant data gap exists regarding the internal audit profession in South Asia, hindering strategic decision-making for organisations. Collaboration among research institutions and professional bodies is recommended to gather and analyse detailed data on the

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profession, including the number of professionals, gender distribution, and challenges faced. This research can provide actionable insights, helping organisations improve policies and enhance governance and risk management frameworks.

Conclusion: Charting a Course for a More Equitable Future in Audit

The internal audit profession's pursuit of gender diversity constitutes a strategic imperative in strengthening governance and institutional resilience, rather than being viewed solely as a social responsibility. The compelling evidence from global data highlights both significant progress in some regions and persistent, deep-rooted challenges in others, particularly across South Asia. The "leaky

pipeline" remains a critical issue, indicating that systemic barriers continue to impede women's advancement into leadership roles despite their growing entry-level participation. These reframing positions gender equity as integral to audit quality, stakeholder trust, and sustainable organisational performance.

However, the transformative success of BRAC's Internal Audit Department in Bangladesh offers a powerful testament to the possibility of overcoming these formidable challenges. By adopting a deliberate, multi-phased strategy underpinned by unwavering leadership commitment, a focus on addressing specific practical barriers, comprehensive support for well-being, and a sustained effort to cultivate an

inclusive culture, BRAC has achieved remarkable and measurable improvements in women's representation, leadership, and retention. This experience demonstrates that organisational will and a strategic, empathetic approach can indeed counteract deeply entrenched societal limitations.

While challenges persist, particularly in regions where cultural norms and infrastructural limitations create significant hurdles, BRAC's model provides a clear blueprint for action. It underscores that a "silver bullet" approach is ineffective; instead, sustained, integrated efforts across policy, culture, and operational practices are required for meaningful and lasting change. The path forward for the internal audit profession globally involves embracing similar strategic, empathetic, and data-driven approaches. By doing so, organisations can not only build a more equitable and inclusive future but also enhance their resilience, effectiveness, and overall contribution to robust corporate governance.

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Opinion Piece

Corruption Swallowing Bangladesh Economy

M Aminul Islam

The Author is a Senior Journalist and Newspaper Columnist based in Dhaka

The article was reviewed by Dr. Jamshed S A Choudhury FCA

Introduction

Corruption and politics are the inseparable bedfellows, continually corroding the economy and the ideal business climate in Bangladesh, which was once known as an investment hub. It is because of an unholy tie-up between politics and economics that virtually begets corruption and sharp business practice. This big business-politics game has been at play for years only to feed coterie interests of a particular community. Look at the modern road infrastructure and a network of flyover, elevated expressway, bus rapid transit and metro rail in Dhaka—they are all “relievers” of traffic congestion. Look at the street furniture—they really look breathtakingly beautiful. Traffic calming and off-limit measures are also “in place”. Think about four-lane and six-lane motorway communication corridors, Jamuna, Padma and other road-rail bridges—they all are built for faster commuting as they have shortened our distance and saved our valuable time. Hence, my heart swells with a proud feeling of having a good communication network. But the same heart sinks when pondering how graft stories behind building those physical facilities filled column inches almost daily. Things have not changed, so has not the system. Corruption is making headlines even today!

State of Bangladesh

While returning home from my workstation by CNG-run auto in late August, I was thinking of the commission of year-round road and pavement renovation and the amount of corruption behind such works. My current stream of consciousness is full of those corrupt minds and souls involved in sleaze, bribery, deception or other vices. Most of the corrupt officials are aided and abetted by rent-seeking politicians whose main business is making oodles of money out of government projects in the name of price hike, cost overrun and multiple work extensions. Nonetheless, missing a project deadline is very commonplace. It is alleged that fraudsters find loopholes to take up projects up to Tk 50 crore that need not seek the rubber stamp from the Executive Committee of the National Economic Council.

Sadly, Bangladesh has slid into the depths of corruption over the years. Previously, it earned the notoriety of being the most corrupt nation. Corruption was the corollary of a systemic change within the political superstructure of the country. Systemic corruption reached cosmic proportions that rocked the once unassailable political superstructure of the Sheikh Hasina regime! Today's interim government of Dr Mohammad Yunus, which is the denouement of the 2024 youthquake, is also

called into question over graft allegations very often. In preceding weeks, unsolicited turns and twists in the political landscape have made people like me unhappy as the road to democracy is so rocky. The path is not paved with gold. It is natural that anarchy reigns after the fall of the despotic regime of the demonic Hasina, and it sets in motion political topsy-turvy. However, I am not so upset about the future as election season is upcoming. But corruption is such a vice that cannot be swallowed and purged so easily. This endemic vice has long been haunting Bangladesh.

State of Economy

The economy of Bangladesh has been navigating a period of acute pressure, shaped by entrenched corruption and persistent structural weaknesses across public administration, procurement, customs, law enforcement and state-owned enterprises. The national corruption-buster ACC's enforcement record has long been criticised for selective action, and high-profile graft cases mostly remain stalled in courts. The global graft watchdog TIB consistently ranks Bangladesh among its corruption-prone South Asian peers, with businesses citing

bribery, cronyism and rent-seeking as key hurdles to fair competition.

Bangladesh is facing multiple headwinds on the economic front. Inflation, particularly food inflation, has remained higher despite government subsidies and import facilitation measures. Taka has depreciated sharply in recent years, increasing the cost of essential imports like fuel and raw materials. Foreign-exchange reserves have come under pressure due to a widening current account deficit, sluggish remittance growth and a slowdown in export earnings from the ready-made garment sector. The World Bank and IMF have warned that unless governance improves and structural reforms are implemented, medium-term growth could fall further. Private investment is subdued, with businesses citing policy unpredictability, weak contract enforcement and high borrowing costs as deterrents. High levels of corruption indicate broader issues with weak governance. There is a need to move away from elite-biased policies and prioritise public interest to hold power accountable.

Types of Corruption

There are different forms of corruption—bribery, palm-greasing, influence-peddling, profiteering, malfeasance,

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misconduct or misrule. Bribery or palm-greasing, as it indicates, is used to secure illicit advantages or gains in politics, business or file movement in offices in exchange for money or favours. Hasina and her subservient cronies and administrative yes-men are a classic case in point here. Influence-peddling is done by an individual who uses his/her influence in return for any work. In this case, the influencer may not be inclined to accept bribes or offer any bribe. It is the use of position or political power on behalf of someone. Dr Yunus and his charmed circles are a case in point here. His Grameen entities got a new life since his post-uprising assumption of the interim setup in the interregnum, let alone the approval of Grameen University and digital wallet service Samadhan.

There are 'ism' suffix-added words like adventurism, ageism, colonialism, cronyism, favouritism, fascism, imperialism, nepotism, obscurantism, parochialism, racism, regionalism, religionism, sectarianism, sexism and terrorism to name but a few. These negative 'isms' are heavy in weight and dangerous in meaning. For example, cronyism is the appointment of friends and associates to positions of authority disregarding their qualifications. Again, favouritism is the practice of giving unfair preferential treatment to one person or group at the expense of another, say, the placement of sons and daughters of high-profile government officials in good positions of the same department. Such isms are vices too. Never forget the supercharged ism 'fascism' that led to the fall of a long-held authoritarian regime only last year.

Corruption at Public Offices

Let me delve deep into sharp practices and shenanigans in the public sector, where bureaucratic corruption at all levels remains a major impediment. Corruption in the form of fraudulence and irregularity at public offices is pervasive. We tend to forget that corruption is corruption, be it of Tk 1.0 only or Tk 1.0 crore. The nation has not forgotten the pillowcase-procurement corruption and how public servants were grossly involved in this monetary vice. Again, there are hundreds of corrupt officials and even petty employees at education offices who always try to find faults of petty, low-paid primary teachers to realise some money, be it Tk 50 or 100. Why? Ain't they public servants? Ain't the public paying them wages for what they deliver?

Another example of rampant corruption is land registration offices across the country. Sub-registry offices are a cesspit of corruption. Sub-registers or boro sahebs are the kingpins of corruption and irregularities at every turn and corner of their desks. Go and check if you accomplish your deed unhindered without making them happy with moolah. So, all sub-registrars must be brought under investigation, and the corrupt

ones and their enablers be booked for trial if found guilty of bribery, forgery or counterfeiting. Otherwise, no positive changes, as we expect in the neo-liberation formula, will be likely there.

Overindulgence is a sort of corruption of minds. One year into the historic July Uprising, many ambitious student leaders still strut and stride in the corridors of power and use state patronage in feeding parochialism. Their wholesale meddling of state affairs in the name of putting things in place is an act of sheer whim. Again, mob justice (read violence) by vigilantes creates anarchy all over. The use of youth power is the need of the hour, but, by the same token, students should brace for a brighter tomorrow. A protector turns into a predator

when power comes unchallenged, but the power-wielders must keep in mind that “With great power comes great responsibility”.

Dr Serajul Islam Chowdhury, an emeritus professor of English at Dhaka University and a much-revered scholar, at a programme in Dhaka in August asserted that Bangladesh endured British and Pakistani colonialism only to become a colony of the wealthy today. While past colonisers pillaged and plundered our resources, now the ‘independent’ Bangladesh sees a privileged class looting and laundering wealth abroad. A former secretary, ABM Abdus Sattar, also dropped a bomb that a handful of interim advisers are mired in massive corruption, alleging that no major

appointments or transfers are made without prior deals with those advisers in question. However, the government outright rejected his unsubstantiated allegations of misconduct against unnamed advisers.

Corruption-Economy Nexus

Institutionalised corruption poses a major obstacle to economic development in Bangladesh despite decades of robust GDP growth. In its 2024 corruption index, the Berlin-based Transparency International ranked Bangladesh 151st out of 180 countries. The Yunus government, which took office in August 2024, also acknowledged entrenched corruption and its impact on the economy, with households losing significant amounts in bribes to access services. While Bangladesh will soon graduate as a developing country, corruption risks in key sectors like RMG and ecological initiatives stymie sustainable growth. Efforts to fight corruption are marred by politicisation and crackdowns on anti-graft activists.

The corruption problem is closely linked to politics-business ties. Major contracts and licences are frequently awarded through opaque processes to politically connected firms, discouraging

Corruption Swallowing Bangladesh Economy

foreign investment and undermining public trust. In sectors like infrastructure, inflated project costs and delays are par for the course. In banking, weak oversight and politically linked loan defaults have deepened a non-performing loan crisis. This culture of impunity diverts resources away from public services and distorts economic priorities.

The interplay of corruption and economic fragility has dire social consequences. Rising living costs are eroding real incomes, putting more households in abject poverty. Youth unemployment is a growing headache, with limited job creation. Again, donor agencies have expressed concern that weak institutional capacity and lack of transparency in public finance management could undermine the efficacy of foreign aid. So, Bangladesh's economic

resilience is being tested by the dual weight of systemic corruption and macroeconomic strain. Without political will to reform institutions, strengthen the rule of law and ensure transparent economic governance, recovery risks ultimately leave the country to rot.

Key Analytical Findings

A December 2024 'White Paper on the State of the Bangladesh Economy' exposed extensive corruption under the fallen Sheikh Hasina regime. The key revelations show illicit financial outflows as an estimated \$16 billion was siphoned off annually between 2009 and 2023. Again, loan scams have left the most corruption-ravaged banking sector in crisis. Inflated project costs and bribery are also a pounding headache. Huge tax exemptions and systemic evasion have deprived the state of critical resources.

Impact on the Economy

Corruption affects the economy at multiple levels, exacerbating existing challenges. While Bangladesh has grown despite bad governance (a Bangladesh paradox), experts warn that this is not sustainable, especially as the country graduates from its least-developed country status. Despite decades of sustained economic growth, endemic corruption poses a challenge to future economic expansion. A vicious cycle of loan defaults, capital flight and manipulation of economic data has eroded confidence in the financial system.

Corruption remains the biggest hurdle for businesses, increasing costs and uncertainty, thereby hindering private investment. The burden of corruption and bribery disproportionately affects the poor who have to pay for basic services. Economists link high inflation to market manipulation and syndication, often enabled by corrupt practices. A 2023 TIB survey found that households paid billions in bribes to access services from various public and private institutions, with 70.9 percent encountering corruption in a single year.

What Lies Ahead

Bangladesh turns 54 this year! It is not too early to say it is still a fledgling nation. It is rather a young nation since life begins at

40! On a downbeat note, the otherwise upbeat expatriate writer and researcher Raiful Alam has lamented the fact that Bangladesh is 54 years old now, yet he sadly shares that our dear country does not think deeply about the assurance of people's voting rights, procurement of modern fighter jets, establishment of modern hospitals and no world-famous universities! Thousands of Raifuls living abroad have the same perception about their motherland. They are critical of a sorry state of affairs with a push for corrections through amending all things wrong and setting priorities right.

Amid all bad things about corruption has surfaced a piece of good news—the arrangement of the 13th general election. The Yunus administration is committed to being a truest and truest overseer of the country's finest and fairest election in its history through ensuring true enfranchisement in a real-sense-of-the-term festivity. The nation's election watchdog, the Election Commission of Bangladesh, is preparing fully to present the polls. Unlike the past

three dummy, midnight elections done during the Hasina regime, the voters, who are the real power of a democracy, await the 2026 general election with bated breath. Now is time to see an inclusive, participatory and credible election.

Concluding Remarks

Now that the nation sees a reformed political landscape as a bellwether for change, the voters never want to see shrewd, unprincipled persons in high places and other positions of power and govern them ever at their sweet will. They do not want to see repeats of the past. Even taxpayers do not want to see civil servants as éminences grises behind government ministers. People always hate the dealers of politics as they are power-mad snollygosters—they are greedy rent-seekers. In the name of standing by humanity, they count time when to grab power and plunder the country's resources. It can, therefore, be said that the public are smart enough today and know how to throw outrageous Machiavellian

politicians out of political office. They know how to resist oligarchs and their allies and cronies who are parachuted into such positions controversially.

To sum up, there is no room for corruption anywhere. Corrupt practices must end everywhere. The corrupt must be spotted and meted out condign punishment through timely trial and through correcting professional misconduct and changing corrupt mindset. It is guaranteed that society will change automatically. The interim government should keep its corruption-busting bandwagon alive for the party that will be in power next to follow suit.

Sources of Info and Acknowledgement

The opinion expressed in this corruption-related opinion piece is the writer's own. However, facts and figures garnered from the information superhighway have also contributed to making it more analytical, insightful and illustrative.

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Shubhashish Bose

Chief Executive Officer (CEO)
The Institute of Chartered Accountants of Bangladesh
CA Bhaban, 100 Kazi Nazrul Islam Avenue
Kawran Bazar, Dhaka-1215, Bangladesh
Tel: +88 09609612100, +88-02-9115340, 9117521
E-mail: ceo@icab.org.bd, sds@icab.org.bd
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Chief Executive Officer (CEO)

The Institute of Chartered Accountants of Bangladesh

CA Bhaban, 100 Kazi Nazrul Islam Avenue

Kawran Bazar, Dhaka-1215, Bangladesh

Tel: +88 09609612100, +88-02-9115340, 9117521

E-mail: ceo@icab.org.bd, sds@icab.org.bd

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100 Kazi Nazrul Islam Avenue, Dhaka 1215

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Recognition of ICAB membership by ICAEW

Membership Scheme of The Institute of Chartered Accountants of England and Wales (ICAEW) allows the members of ICAB to apply for ICAEW membership based on their experiences.

Eligibility criteria of this membership scheme are a series of questions which assess ICAB Member's experience, achievements, skills and expertise. Each application must be supported by an eligible sponsor. Applicants need to complete an Examination of Experience.

Details of ICAEW Membership Scheme is available at <http://www.icaew.com/membership/becoming-a-member/members-of-other-bodies/campaigns/pathways-to-membership>.

ICAB signed its first Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with the Institute of Chartered Accountants in England and Wales (ICAEW) in 2009. Since then, ICAB has been working with ICAEW as the learning and professional development partner, and also recognized as an approved tuition provider of ICAEW.

As per MoU, ICAB Members can be the members of ICAEW after successful completion of 04 papers out of 15. These members have the opportunity to apply for UK Practising Certificate (PC) subject to meeting the standard ICAEW PC requirement.

Recognition of ICAB Membership by CIPFA, UK

Members of the Institute of Chartered Accountants of Bangladesh (ICAB) are eligible to apply for membership of the Chartered Institute of Public Finance and Accountancy (CIPFA), a globally recognised membership body for the public sector.

An MoU between ICAB and CIPFA, UK was signed on 28 January 2017. Under this MoU, an ICAB member can also become a members of CIPFA subject to fulfillment of certain criteria.

An ICAB Member with good standing having five or more years post-qualification public sector experience are eligible for Full Membership of CIPFA as Chartered Public Finance Accountant (CIPFA) and the members having fewer than five years post-qualification public sector experience are eligible as Affiliate member of CIPFA (CIPFA Affiliat).

ICAB members having CIPFA Affiliate membership, or having no working experience in public sector can gain CIPFA status with the successful completion of exams of only two papers i.e. Public Sector Financial Reporting and Strategic Public Finance.

Membership through Chartered Accountants Australia & New Zealand (CA ANZ) International Pathway Program (IPP)

The Institute of Chartered Accountants of Bangladesh (ICAB) signed an MoU with the Chartered Accountants Australia & New Zealand (CA ANZ). Under this, ICAB members living in Australia or New Zealand having five years post qualification experience at anywhere will be eligible to be member of CA ANZ after successful completion of CA ANZ International Pathway Program (IPP).

There will be no requirement of passing CA ANZ general route examinations by eligible ICAB members as their International Pathway Program (IPP) workshop through case studies would examine the contemporary Australasian business, accounting and finance environment relevant for members of ICAB. On the other hand, CA ANZ members can also be members of ICAB subject to having Bangladeshi citizenship and other requirements as prescribed by ICAB Bye-laws.

Membership of the International Valuation Standards Council (IVSC)

Efforts are underway for ICAB to Become a member of the International Valuation Standards Council (IVSC). This would create an opportunity for the members of ICAB to involve in the valuation process of local and foreign investment in Bangladesh.

This would allow Chartered Accountants to put up their highly essential services and play positive roles in attracting foreign investment. With regard to this, ICAB has already conducted a Members Conference. More so, a virtual meeting with the CEO of IVSC was held on 8 June 2021 where the IVSC proposed ICAB to become member of IVSC on pro-rata basis.

Other Memberships

ICAB is an active member of International Federation of Accountants (IFAC), Confederation of Asian and Pacific Accountants (CAPA) and South Asian Federation of Accountants (SAFA). ICAB is also an associate member of Chartered Accountants Worldwide (CAW).